

Calculating visual binaries' orbits should it ever be fully automated?

Discussing 13 stars with 8 first-time orbits

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Abstract

Many methods have been devised to compute orbits and they fall into two main categories: geometric approaches and analytic ones. Geometric methods deliver orbital elements less certain but are useful when the length of the arc observed so far is just more or less significant of the entire trajectory to come. More and more often though, analytical methods are being used to kind of automatically compute orbits for double stars having only traveled a small part of their entire orbit. This is undoubtedly due to the widespread availability of computers and of specialized computer programs enabling the straightforward calculation of orbits out of a set of observations without requiring from the operator a grasp of the binaries that he models finally just in an abstract and distant way. One should remember that Couteau (1978) considered the computation of orbits as a craftsman job for various reasons and Worley (1990) questioned the usefulness of some orbits that appear more like computing efforts than good astronomical sense. This paper will not be a quarrel of the ancients and the moderns, but will remind traditional ways of computing orbits so that it will remain, for those who wish, a rewarding craftsman job of playing with a wire and two pins, keeping a close contact with the specificity of the binaries studied and thereof of the observations made, to first find with their best astronomical sense, the foci of the apparent ellipse. The calculation of the orbits and ephemeris of 13 stars will serve as example, and for eight of them first-time original orbital solutions are proposed, computed by means of the geometrical method confirming its appropriateness and reliability.

I. Introduction

Many methods have been devised to compute orbits since Savary (1827), Herschel (1833, 1850), Klinkerfues (1855) and they fall into two main categories: geometric approaches (van de Kamp, 1947), (Baize, 1954) and analytic ones (Van den Bos, 1962), (Arend, 1941, 1961, 1968), (Dommanget, 1959), (Binnendijke, 1960) to quote a few and new methods keep emerging every decade or so, as if the tens of methods available were neither satisfactory nor sufficient. This is the proof that no method in itself offers “the” solution, each having strengths and weaknesses, but as reminded by Couteau (1978), geometric methods deliver orbital elements less certain but are useful when the length of the arc observed so far is just more or less significant of the entire trajectory to come. Of the more than 100.000 binaries in the WDS, less than 2% have an orbit and just a quarter of them have an orbit grade better than 3 and only a few of the latter have definitive orbital parameters. It means that most of the work remaining to be done deals with stars having incomplete trajectories over a limited portion of their trajectories and geometric methods remain in that case a good if not the best choice. Nevertheless, the current trend, with the widespread availability of

powerful PCs, is that more and more often analytical methods are being used to kind of automatically compute orbits for double stars having only travelled a small part of their entire orbit (Docobo and Ling, 2003), (Ling 2010), using advanced techniques that sometimes do not even requires to get a value of the areal constant as for Docobo’s analytical method (1985), where measures appear to be somehow weighted according to the size of the instrument and observing means. Curiously enough, this would lead to affect the lowest value to Couteau’s measurements in Docobo and Ling computations (2003) whereas Couteau is the discoverer himself in the first place of all the stars studied, with the smallest instrument, i.e. a 50 cm refractor and a filar micrometer. Recently some authors have devised new methods, for example Branham (2005) proposes an analytic method based on semi-definite programming that incorporates the areal constant and that should be insensitive to outliers when appropriate data reduction criterion are being used. Nevertheless, one should remember that Couteau (1978) considered the computation of orbits as a craftsman job for various reasons (some reminded in Appendix A) and Worley (1990) questioned the usefulness of some orbits that appear more like computing efforts than good astronomical practice or sense.

The geometrical method will be used in this paper to compute the orbits of 13 double stars, 9 of them entirely new, paying a lot of attention to obtaining a somehow stable areal constant across sectors, so that the projected law of areas be obeyed (Van de Kamp, 1961), before going any further into the determination of the orbit elements and ephemeris. Sometimes, the initial ellipse one draws through the cloud of observations is very far from the final ellipse that satisfies better the law of areas (e.g. A 552 in this paper). As a hint, Danjon (1952) reminds that the more the curve $\theta(t)$ departs from a straight line, the more elliptical the appropriate solution will be, and he elaborates on the case of A88, a very difficult object, for which the scatter could look nearly circular, whereas the study of $\theta(t)$ suggests an eccentric ellipse as a final solution. This paper will not be a quarrel of the ancients and the moderns, but will remind traditional ways of computing orbits so that it will remain, for those who wish, a rewarding craftsman job of playing with a wire and two pins to first find with their common sense the foci of the apparent ellipse. It also reminds us the great pedagogic value of geometric methods for those wishing to start computing orbits, as they compel the operator to be respectful of the characteristics of the observations and of the phenomenon observed and represented. Then for each star, we will derive individual stellar masses whenever possible based either on the trigonometric parallax, the dynamic parallax or both and will introduce “mass convergence tables” where the absolute magnitudes, individual masses and parallax are determined by small incremental refinements after a short ten step iteration.

Object	ALPHA2K	DELTA2K	BD	ADS	HIP	mag1	mag2	Sp _a	Orbit	π_{trigo} b	$\pm e - \pi_{\text{trigo}}$
RST 3340	00:05:05	-18,36-19,8447			TYC5841 579 1	10,4	10,4	G0	NO		
HU 616	06:54:01	33,4133,1427		554433145		9,1	9,5	F0	NO	2,57	0,61
HU 841	07:40:00	66,0366,518		622837353		9	9	G	NO	7,54	1,44
A 552	08:44:04	-4,12-03,2454		696442863		7,5	8,5	A2	NO	5,69	0,93
A 2554	08:53:09	1,4902,2088		707443676		8	10,2	F0	2	14,79	1,02
BU 796	12:17:05	6,3607,2529		850059916		8	8,8	F2	NO	7,21	0,45
RST 4502	12:34:09	-5,09-04,3307		61322		8,6	8,6	A5	NO	3,76	0,61
A 1097 AB	14:02:00	57,1357,1478		908968554		7,8	8,1	F5	3	6,82	0,69
HU 337	19:18:09	17,3617,3924		1230194911		8,6	9	A3	NO	4,15	1,18
HO 137	20:40:05	29,4929,4131		14149102033		6,5	11	A0	NO	13,47	0,46
BU 838	21:20:09	3,0802,4343		14880105399		7,6	9,6	F8	1	14,09	0,99
STF 2822 AB	21:44:01	28,4528,4169		15270107310		4,7	6,1	F5	3	44,97	0,43
HU 497 BC	23:17:05	16,5216,4896		16648115002		9,5	10	F2III	3	6,74	1,45

Table 1: 13 stars of which 8 are first-time orbits are computed with latest observations

^a all are main sequence unless otherwise indicated

^b milli-arcsec or mas (SIMBAD)

^c average error of 10% of mas up to 100 pc

The main characteristics of the 13 stars studied in this paper, are summarized in Table1, with their 2000 celestial coordinates, catalog references, i.e. (BD, ADS and HIP), their apparent magnitudes and spectral types, existence of a published orbit in the USNO Sixth Catalog of Orbits of Visual Binary Stars (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017), trigonometric parallax if any available (ESA, 1997), and error on parallax (Perryman, 2009). Eight of them have no previously known orbits according to the USNO Sixth Catalog of Orbits of Visual Binary Stars and we provide completely new original orbit solutions and masses. As stated by Tokovinin (2016) the main reason for publishing here uncertain first-time orbits remains the need to understand the orbital motion and to plan further observations for their improvement, not leaving interesting stars neglected.

II. How to properly use the geometric method

Computing an orbit with the geometric method is very straightforward and the reader will refer to the material published to get a thorough understanding of the underlying theory and practice (van de Kamp, 1947), (Baize, 1954), (Couteau, 1978). Nevertheless, it can be worthwhile to remind the successive stages to be performed, insisting on the careful handling of the various steps. The position angles θ of the set of observations need to be corrected and brought back to the same equinox as the celestial pole has drifted over the time span during which the measures have been made, coordinates (α, δ) are expressed in degrees, t_0 being the epoch chosen for the equinox and t the epoch of the observation.

$$\Delta\theta = -0,0056 \sin \alpha \cdot \sec \delta (t - t_0)$$

where the secant function $\sec \delta = 1/\cos \delta$. One should notice that by choosing t_0 as close as possible to the beginning of the series of measurements, corrections will be small or negligible. One should also notice that the precession-correction is greater near the celestial pole and it shrinks rapidly once you are more than 20° from the pole and is obviously null for $\delta = 0$. For declination less than about 80° the tiny correction can be most of the time ignored. Position angles become:

$$\theta_t = \theta_0 - \Delta\theta$$

Proper motion also slightly changes the position angles. The correction is written as follows:

$$\Delta\theta = -0,00417 \cdot \mu_\alpha \cdot \sin \delta (t - t_0)$$

where μ_α (i.e. the proper motion) is expressed in seconds of time per year for right ascension (RA) as in here. Again, it is only for binaries having strong proper motions and located close to the pole that the correction will yield significant values.

So, basically one might reasonably consider that for binaries having a declination δ lower than 70° , raw data from the excel sheet might be used, otherwise they can easily be corrected using the previous formulae. As the four binaries of this study have a $\delta < 60^\circ$, no correction have been applied to the measurements.

The next step aims at generating a plot of all the observations, after having transformed the polar coordinates (θ, ρ) into Cartesian or rectangular coordinates, so that they could be easily plotted on a graph.

With $x = \rho \cos \theta$ and $y = \rho \sin \theta$ and

conversely $\rho = (x^2 + y^2)^{1/2}$ and $\theta = \arctg y/x$

The plot obtained can be printed out at different arbitrary scale so that it would offer a convenient support for the most important part of the job, namely drawing the apparent ellipse with a thread and two pins. This work is somehow subjective, as the drawing of the ellipse must make it pass

through the most reliable observations (at least as close as possible) and globally limit the deviations from most of the remaining points. While drawing the orbit through the set of observations and checking the areal constant for various sectors, one should remember that θ is more important and less error prone than ρ as reminded by Jonckheere (1950), especially for close binaries measured with a visual micrometer or sometimes just assessed on the Airy disk aspect. Of course, many factors influence what one can expect of a measurement, 5 to even 10 degrees of dispersion on θ on a tight binary with a significant difference of magnitude Δm between the pair is less troublesome than a few degrees on an easy couple. Then, one must cope with the vast heterogeneity of observers, instruments (i.e. mainly refractors and reflectors of all sizes and configurations), micrometers (e.g. wire / filar, double image, diffraction based, etc.) (Baize, 1949), (Jonckheere, 1950), (Minois, 1984), webcams or video cams, CCDs (Buil, 1991), (Soulié and Morlet, 1997), (Salaman and Morlet 2000), (Gili and Bonneau, 2001), (Morlet and Salaman, 2005) or EMCCDs (Gili and Agati, 2009), speckle (Bonneau, 1993), (Mason and Hartkopf, 2017) and now sophisticated cameras, e.g. (Gili *et al.*, 2014) or a combination of these as basic observations, the older being moreover often the most interesting ones given the long duration of orbital motions. The tracing of the curves $\rho(t)$ and $\theta(t)$, especially the latter, as suggested by Couteau (1978) and Dommanget (2000), and their adjustment in order to establishing a satisfactory areal constant enables an assessment of how representative the observations are and of their corresponding quality that does not enable an automated procedure or program, that somehow remains blind to that.

The principal star A is not at the center of the ellipse as we deal with the projection of the real ellipse onto the sky along the observation line. Once a reasonable ellipse has been achieved, which is not always obvious, far from it, the next step is to select 5 to 6 points corresponding to the best observations (somehow equally distributed) and to link them to star A to use the planimeter to measure in arbitrary units the surface of the sectors defined. The planimeter used is the model n°313 E from HAFF (<https://www.haff.de/>) and is very convenient.

Figure 1: Planimeter model n°313 E from HAFF

If S_n is the surface of a sector n and Δt_n the time taken by the companion to run through it, the areal constant will be obtained by: $c = S_n / \Delta t_n$ and this constant must be the same (at a few hundredth) for the various sectors, this leading sometimes to significantly alter the original outline chosen for the ellipse, adjusting the length of the wire, changing the position of the pins or both at the same time until one gets a sense not of accomplishment but of minimal frustration as so rare are the orbits that fit perfectly “head on” the observations. This constant c is the direct result of the second Kepler’s law, i.e. that the radius vector sweeps out equal areas in equal times (Tatum, 2023). Once a satisfactory apparent ellipse is drawn, the final position of the two pins must be spotted carefully (among the various attempts leaving holes in the sheet) as they represent the foci of the ellipse and all further work and measurements will depend on them. Then one should determine the scale, usually in millimeters per arc sec.

The center of the ellipse, C is of course located on the line joining the 2 foci and in the middle of them and will serve as the origin of a new set of axis, (ξ, η) that will be used to measure the Thiele-Innes constants directly on the drawing (Figure 2). Tracing a line through the center C and star A

(segment CA) will deliver a point on the ellipse, i.e. P the periastron and to find the conjugate diameter to CP, one draws parallel strings to CP the middle of which lead to point R. As the observed ellipse is a projection of the true ellipse, one should not expect P and R to necessarily fall anywhere near the semi-major axis or semi-minor axis of the apparent ellipse. One just need to work as neatly as possible, as one would do with a technical drawing. Now the eccentricity can be readily computed by simply dividing two segments measured on the drawing:

$$e = CA/CP$$

Figure 2: The geometrical method, from Couteau (1978) corrected as North is down, East is right (the orbit is as if observed through the instrument) and the new set of axis (ξ, η) is oriented similarly to (x, y).

Now let's consider the Thiele-Innes constants, noted A, B, F, G, C, H (which determine the plane of the true orbit and its size) and

$$F_1 = F \cdot \cos \varphi \text{ and } G_1 = G \cdot \cos \varphi \text{ where } \varphi = \arcsin e$$

and e the eccentricity already obtained;

one should first take note that if we take the center of the apparent ellipse C as the origin of a new set of axis (ξ, η) parallel to the old ones and oriented in a similar way, then for a point of true anomaly u:

$$\xi = A \cdot \cos u + F_1 \cdot \sin u$$

$$\eta = B \cdot \cos u + G_1 \cdot \sin u$$

and the Thiele-Innes constants A and B are simply measured on the graph as the coordinates of P with respect to the centre C axis (ξ, η) and the measure of the coordinates of the point R delivers:

$$\xi_r = F_1 \text{ and } \eta_r = G_1$$

In the example of Figure 2, coordinates of P, $\xi_p = A > 0$ and $\eta_p = B > 0$, R is found following the arrow along the motion of the companion, and in that case $\xi_r = F_1 < 0$ and $\eta_r = G_1 > 0$. It is important to pay attention to the signs of the coordinates of A, B, F_1 , G_1 , as filling the spreadsheet cells with values having the wrong signs obviously ruins the computation.

Knowing F_1 , G_1 and $\cos \varphi$ enable to calculate $F = F_1 / \cos \varphi$ and $G = G_1 / \cos \varphi$.

We now have c, e, A, B, F, G and can calculate $x_c = -Ae$ and $y_c = -Bc$ and $CA = (x_c^2 + y_c^2)^{1/2}$

The dynamic elements: **P** period in years, **n** the mean motion, **T** the epoch of the passage at periastron, **e** eccentricity, **a** semi-major axis will be obtained by simple calculations made with measurements on the drawing. The geometric elements of Campbell: **i** the inclination, **Ω** the angle of position of the line of nodes (i.e. the intersection of the object's orbital plane with the plane of reference), also referred to as the position angle of the first node, i.e. the node whose position angle is less than 180°, known as the longitude of ascending node, and **ω** the angle between the node and periastron (i.e. the argument of periastron defines the orientation of the ellipse in the orbital plane, as an angle measured from the ascending node to the periastron in the direction of motion of the secondary), will be obtained by various calculations using the Thiele-Innes constants, i.e. A, B, F and G..

Once the orbit is drawn and the coordinates of P and R have been measured we have made a significant part of the work, obtaining:

P = S / c is done by dividing in arbitrary surface units, the surface of the ellipse by the areal constant. The surface of the ellipse is the result of a direct measure with the planimeter and c, the areal constant, has been determined by an average of several c_i obtained measuring successive sectors $c_i = S_i / \Delta t_i$ with S_i = surface of sector i traveled during time Δt_i and finally we have $c = (\sum_i S_i / \Delta t_i) / n$ for n sectors. One can also create a double diagram $[(\rho, \theta) ; (\theta, t)]$ as already proposed Herschel (1933) to check the areal constant as reminded by Dommanget (2000);

n = 360 / P, it is the annual mean motion in degrees also referred to as $\mu = 2\pi / P$ in radians;

T = average of several measures (T1,T2,T3) where $T_1 = t_{B1} + (\text{area } B_1AP) / c$; $T_2 = t_{B2} + (\text{area } B_2AP) / c$; $T_3 = t_{B3} + (\text{area } B_3AP) / c$ areas measured with the planimeter on the drawing of the apparent ellipse. T can also directly be read on the curve $\theta(t)$;

e = CA / CP directly measured on the orbit's drawing ; also $e = \sin \varphi$ where the ellipse is the projection of the principal circle (eccentric circle or, preferably, the auxiliary circle) from a plane tilted of an angle φ ;

a = the semi-major axis is directly measured on the orbit's drawing and given the scale converted in arc sec or else given by $a = [(A \cdot G - B \cdot F) / \cos i]^{1/2}$;

then the measurement on the orbit's drawing of the coordinates of P and R according to axis (ξ, η) , leads to the Thiele-Innes constants A, B, F₁, G₁, we can also obtain (given $\varphi = \arcsin e$) F and G therefore the first four constants from which we will compute i, Ω, ω, let's see how.

Let's introduce the constants $C_1 = (B - F) / (A + G)$ and $C_2 = (B + F) / (A - G)$ then Ω is given by:

$$\Omega = (\arctg C_1 + \arctg C_2) / 2 ;$$

ω = $\arctg C_1 - \Omega$, i.e. the argument of periastron (ω);

Let's finally introduce the constant $C_3 = [(B + F) \cdot \sin (\Omega + \omega)] / [(B - F) \cdot \sin (\Omega - \omega)]$

as $\text{tg}^2 (i/2) = C_3$ one can easily compute that:

$$i = \arcsin [(C_3 - 1) / (C_3 + 1)] \text{ or else } i = 2 \arctg (C_3)^{1/2}$$

By inputting the values P, scale (mm/arc sec), e, A, B, F₁, G₁ one gets in an excel spreadsheet immediately Ω, ω, i and a in arc sec. We provide the spreadsheet as complementary data to the present paper. Inputting in a different excel sheet P, n, T, e, a, i, Ω, ω, t₀, Δt, one gets the ephemeris and the drawing of the corresponding ellipse.

Let's see how one can get an ephemeris using the aforementioned orbital elements. We have two equations for that:

$$\text{tg} (\theta - \Omega) = \text{tg} (v + \omega) \cos i \quad (1,II)$$

from which we will derive θ and where v is the true anomaly;

$$\rho = r \left[\frac{\cos(v + \omega)}{\cos(\theta - \omega)} \right] \quad (2, \text{II})$$

Where:

$$r = \frac{a \cdot (1 - e^2)}{(1 + e \cdot \cos v)} \quad (3, \text{II})$$

Using (1, II) to compute θ , and (2, II) to compute r for ρ , one will need v , the true anomaly, the only unknown:

$$v = 2 \operatorname{arctg} \left(\sqrt{\frac{(1+e)}{(1-e)}} \cdot \operatorname{tg} \left(\frac{u}{2} \right) \right) \quad (4, \text{II})$$

where u is the eccentric anomaly.

For a long time, astronomers have used a table of the keplerian motion, that gives the true anomaly v (or of $(v - M)$, i.e. equation of the center) as a function of M the mean anomaly (i.e. $M = n(t-T)$) for any possible eccentricity (Danjon, 1952). We are going to detail how one can in 3 small steps perform an iteration in a spreadsheet that will provide an acceptable value of u in (4, II) that we need in order to compute v , the true anomaly. As:

$$u - e \cdot \sin u = M \quad (5, \text{II})$$

we have $u = M + e \cdot \sin u$ and we will make a first approximation with:

$u_0 = M + e \cdot \sin M$ to get a first value of u_0 and compute the error made ε_0 using M instead of u .

As: $e \cdot \sin u_0 = u_0 - M$ therefore, the error ε_0 :

$$\varepsilon_0 = e \cdot \sin u_0 - (u_0 - M) \quad (6, \text{II})$$

by differentiation of $\operatorname{tg} v/2 = [(1+e)/(1-e)]^{1/2} \cdot \operatorname{tg} u/2$ we get

$$\frac{du}{dt} = \frac{\mu}{(1 - e \cdot \cos u)} \text{ with } \mu = \frac{2\pi}{P} \text{ (in radians)} \quad (7, \text{II})$$

Hence:

$$u_1 = u_0 + \frac{du}{dt} \quad (8, \text{II})$$

replacing in (8, II) du/dt with its value in (7, II) we get:

$$u_1 = u_0 + \frac{\varepsilon_0}{(1 - e \cdot \cos u_0)} \quad (9, \text{II})$$

u_1 from which we compute ε_1 :

$$\varepsilon_1 = e \cdot \sin u_1 - (u_1 - M) \quad (10, \text{II})$$

reused to compute u_2 as in (9, II), then ε_2 as in (10, II) and so on until $\varepsilon_n = 0$. Usually three steps are sufficient to make the process converge and get a stable value of u_3 (with residuals $\varepsilon_3 \pm = 0$) which can be used in (4, II) to get v , which was the only unknown in (1, II) and (2, II), thus obtain an ephemeris in (θ, ρ) . This is how works the spreadsheet attached as a dataset to this paper (Poyet, 2017). Note that eq. (5, II) is referred to as Kepler's equation and can be obtained by trivial derivation of (7, II) as demonstrated in Appendix D, more easily than what is proposed for example by Tatum (2023, eq. 9.6.5).

Kepler's equation is transcendental in u and must be solved numerically, convergence by iteration

as aforementioned is also proposed in (Meuss, 2009) and (Boulé *et al.*, 2017). We've also added a sheet "u & v fct of M" which computes any value of u (eccentric anomaly) for any given e and M (input number in yellow cells), and one can check the results against the Table p.432 of Danjon (1952), using a less convergent yet simpler iteration ($u_0=M+e \sin M$, $u_1=M+e \sin u_0$, $u_2=M+e \sin u_1$, ... $u_n=M+e \sin u_{n-1}$) than what is used to compute the ephemeris and described above (example is given in Appendix E for $e=0,35$ and $M=0,25$).

Let's now remind of the various pitfalls one should avoid in order to smoothly move from the orbit's drawing to obtaining the dynamic elements, the elements of Campbell and finally the ephemeris. The first thing to pay attention to is the orientation of the axis on which the scatter of measures is plotted then that the plot preserves equal scales on both axis (beware of software adjustments due to legends or else on the print). Facing the plot, the North should be down (X axis positive readings) and the East at the right (Y axis positive readings) somehow as if you were observing through the eyepiece of an instrument.

All measurements of coordinates should be made according to the new set of axis (ξ, η) passing through C. Coordinates of P are (A,B) and of R (F_1, G_1) according to (ξ, η). One should observe that R is obtained from P in the direction of rotation of the companion star which can be direct (values of θ increase over time) or retrograde (values of θ decrease over time). The smallest error in the drawing, the slightest measurement error spoils the work and ruins the result. Drawing orbits, measuring Thiele-Innes constants and deriving orbital parameters is like directly measuring binaries with a filar micrometer, its a work to be done with care and application.

The great advantage of the geometrical method is that obtaining the orbital parameters requires to maintain a relationship with the data and with the apparent ellipse that one tries to fit to the observations. It's not just putting a batch of observations, filtered or weighted according to the observers and / or their observing means or techniques, into a computer letting it operate as a black box and delivering orbital parameters for sparsely defined trajectories over short segments of an apparent orbit.

III. Obtaining dynamic parallaxes and masses

Computing orbits aims at measuring accurate stellar masses to test evolutionary models of star populations and star formation theories. The short presentation under this section will aim at introducing all the parameters that will be later used in the excel spreadsheet that comes together with this paper. Given the trigonometric parallax, one can immediately compute the sum of the masses for the binary by using the third Kepler's law (the square of the orbital period of a planet is directly proportional to the cube of the semi-major axis of its orbit), e.g. (Tatum, 2023):

$$\mu_A + \mu_B = \frac{a''^3}{p^3 P^2} \quad (1, \text{III})$$

where μ_A and μ_B are the masses of the components A and B given in Solar mass (taken as unity), a''^3 is the semi-major axis in arcsec as explained in the previous section, p^3 is the parallax (i.e. trigonometric or dynamic) and P^2 the period as given by the orbital parameters. As one will notice the relation gives access to the total mass of the system $\mu_A + \mu_B$ and not individual masses.

An approximate relation between the mass and luminosity of main-sequence stars, was predicted by Eddington (1924) and is obtained from a graph of absolute bolometric magnitude against the logarithm of mass (in solar units), i.e. M/M_\odot , for a large number of binary stars. Most points lie on an approximately straight line. Since a star's absolute bolometric magnitude is a function of the logarithm of its luminosity (in solar units), i.e. L/L_\odot , this line is represented by the M-L relation:

$$\log(L / L_\odot) = n \log(M / M_\odot) \text{ and } L / L_\odot = (M / M_\odot)^n$$

where n averages about 3 for bright massive stars, about 4 for Sun-type stars, and about 2.5 for dim red dwarfs of low mass. This Mass-Luminosity Relation (MLR) (Eddington, 1924, 1926) leads to the calculation of dynamic parallaxes (Russell, 1928), (Kuiper, 1938), (Russell and Moore, 1940), (Baize, 1943), (Baize et Romani, 1946), (Baize, 1947), (Harris *et al.*, 1963), (Couteau, 1971), (Dommanget, 1976) enabling the knowledge of each individual mass of the binary system, μ_A and μ_B . Using this method and coupling it to simple iterative calculations in a spreadsheet enable to derive in less than ten iterations stable absolute bolometric magnitudes for each star A and B, individual masses for A and B, the dynamic parallax and the sum of masses to serve as a cross-check.

It is proposed by Mullaney (2005) to initialise the process taking $\mu_A = \mu_B = 1$ therefore $\Sigma\mu_s = 2$ and let converge the process, while the author had independently the same idea starting the iteration with the calculation of the absolute bolometric magnitudes. We will see that both approaches lead to quasi identical results to 10^{-3} on the individual masses. So let's formulate the relationship that express the log of the mass as of the bolometric absolute magnitude:

$$\log_{10}\mu = -k(M - M_{\odot}) \quad (2, \text{III})$$

where μ = the mass in solar units, k used to be 0,1117 (Couteau 1978) but has been revised taking into account hot stars of spectroscopic systems as $k=0,0987$ (McAlister and Hartkopf, 1988) and accepted as such by Couteau (1988, 1994) leading to decrease computed masses (of one to five percents), M the bolometric absolute magnitude of the star and M_{\odot} is absolute magnitude of the Sun = 4,77. The absolute magnitude is the magnitude of the star would it be observed from a 10 parsecs distance. One should notice that we can write:

$\mu_A + \mu_B = \mu_A (1 + \mu_B / \mu_A)$ and using (2, III) we get

$$\mu_A + \mu_B = \mu_A (1 + 10^{-k.(MB-M_{\odot}) + k.(MA-M_{\odot})}) = \mu_A (1 + 10^{-k.(MB-MA)}) = \mu_A (1 + 10^{-k.\Delta m})$$

we pose $D = 1 + 10^{-k.\Delta m}$ then $\mu_A + \mu_B = \mu_A D$

The absolute magnitude, the apparent magnitude and the parallax are linked as follows in the Pogson's formulae:

$$M = m + 5 + 5 \log_{10} p \quad (3, \text{III})$$

where m should be a corrected apparent bolometric magnitude m_b is:

$m_b = m_v + C_v$ where C_v is a function of the spectral type or of the temperature of the star as given in a table as the one from Harris (1963) in Appendix B.

M can be replaced in (2, III) with its value from (3, III)

$$\log_{10}\mu_A = -k(m + 5 + 5 \log_{10} p - M_{\odot}) = -k(m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 - M_{\odot}) - 5k \log_{10} p \quad (4, \text{III})$$

besides from (1) and (2) we have:

$$\mu_A + \mu_B = \mu_A (1 + 10^{-k.\Delta m}) = \frac{a^3}{p^3 P^2} \quad (5, \text{III})$$

to simplify we pose $\alpha^3 = a^3 / P^2$ then we can write:

$$\text{with } \alpha^3 = \frac{a^3}{P^2} \text{ then } \mu_A D = \frac{\alpha^3}{p^3} \quad (6, \text{III})$$

from (6, III) we can write: $\log_{10} \mu_A + \log_{10} D = 3 \log_{10} \alpha - 3 \log_{10} p$ therefore:

$$\log_{10}\mu_A = -3 \log_{10} p + 3 \log_{10} \alpha - \log_{10} D \quad (7, \text{III})$$

and by matching (4, III) and (7, III) we get:

$$-5k \log_{10} p - k(m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 + M_{\odot}) = -3 \log_{10} p + 3 \log_{10} \alpha - \log_{10} D$$

and finally the expression of the parallax:

$$(1 - 5k/3) \log_{10} p = \log_{10} \alpha + k/3 (m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 - M_{\odot}) - (1/3) \cdot \log_{10} D$$

with $\beta_A = (m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 - M_{\odot})$ we get:

$$\left(1 - \frac{5}{3}k\right) \log_{10} p = \log_{10} \alpha + \frac{k}{3} \beta_A - \frac{1}{3} \log_{10} D \quad (8, III)$$

that we will use in our spreadsheet to compute the parallax as $p = 10^{(\log_{10} p)}$

from (4,III) we can extract the value of $\log_{10} p$:

$$\log_{10} p = - (1/5) \cdot (m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 - M_{\odot}) - (\log_{10} \mu_A) / 5k$$

and replace it in (7,III), then we can write:

$$\log_{10} \mu_A = (3/5) \cdot (m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 - M_{\odot}) + (3k/5) \cdot \log_{10} \mu_A + 3 \log_{10} \alpha - \log_{10} D$$

$$\log_{10} \mu_A - (3k/5) \cdot \log_{10} \mu_A = (3/5) \cdot \beta_A + 3 \log_{10} \alpha - \log_{10} D \text{ thus multiplying by 5}$$

$5 \log_{10} \mu_A - (3/k) \cdot \log_{10} \mu_A = 3 \beta_A + 15 \log_{10} \alpha - 5 \log_{10} D$ hence multiplying by -1 and factoring:

$$\left(\frac{3-5k}{k}\right) \cdot \log_{10} \mu_A = 5 \log_{10} D - 3 \beta_A - 15 \log_{10} \alpha \quad (9, III)^1$$

for star B we have a similar equation where β_A is replaced by β_B , i.e. $\beta_B = (m_{vB} + C_{vB} + 5 - M_{\odot})$ and notation D is replaced by D' defined as:

$$D' = 1 + 10^{+k \cdot \Delta m} \quad (10, III)$$

Equations (9, III) and (10, III) directly give the individual masses of A and B without having the need to resort to the parallax, whereas the dynamic parallax only gives their sum (1, III). Equations (8, III) and (9, III) suppose that the spectrum of both components are known. Most of the times we only know the global spectrum and make the assumption that they are identical. The error is negligible as to a very different spectrum correspond a high Δm , and in that case $\log_{10} D$ tends to zero. One will notice the importance of the visual magnitude beyond good orbital parameters, therefore good dynamic parallaxes and reliable masses depend on good photometric measurements.

Finally using (8, III) and replacing the parallax by its expression as a function of the absolute and visual magnitude and expressing the period P, one gets:

$$(1 - (5k/3)) \log_{10} p = \log_{10} (a^3 / P^2)^{1/3} + (k/3) \cdot (m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 - M_{\odot}) - (1/3) \cdot \log_{10} D \text{ therefore}$$

$$(1 - (5k/3)) \log_{10} p = \log_{10} a - (2/3) \cdot \log_{10} P + (k/3) (m_{vA} + C_{vA} + 5 - M_{\odot}) - (1/3) \cdot \log_{10} D \text{ then}$$

$$\log_{10} P = \frac{3}{2} \log_{10} a - \frac{1}{2} \log_{10} D - \frac{k}{2} M_{\odot} + \frac{5k}{2} + \frac{k}{2} (m_{vA} + C_{vA}) - \frac{3}{2} p (1 - \frac{5k}{3}) \quad (11, III)$$

replacing p using (3, III) let's develop the term $-(3/2) p (1-5k/3)$:

$$-(3/2) p (1-5k/3) = -(1-5k/3) (M_A/5) \cdot (3/2) + (1-5k/3) ((m_{vA} + C_{vA})/5) \cdot (3/2) + (1-5k/3) \cdot (3/2)$$

$$\text{i.e. } M_A((k/2)-3/10) + 3/10 (m_{vA} + C_{vA}) - (k/2) \cdot (m_{vA} + C_{vA}) + 3/2 - 5k/2$$

now replacing the term $-3/2 p (1-5k/3)$ by its value in (11, III) we get:

$$\log_{10} P = \frac{3}{2} \log_{10} a - \frac{1}{2} \log_{10} D - \frac{k}{2} M_{\odot} + M_A \left(\frac{k}{2} - \frac{3}{10}\right) + \frac{3}{10} (m_{vA} + C_{vA}) + \frac{3}{2} \quad (12, III)$$

¹ This equation is incorrect in Couteau (1978) eq (60,VI) p. 166

As long as the MLR is followed by the star, equation (12, III) where M_A is taken from Appendix C can be used to get an indicative value of the Period P.

From (1, III) one can also easily get the dynamic parallax:

$$p = \frac{a^3}{((\mu_A + \mu_B) \cdot P^2)^{1/3}} \quad (13, III)$$

Now, using simple iterative calculations in a spreadsheet enables to derive in less than ten iterations stable absolute bolometric magnitudes for each star A and B using equation (3, III) (the first value of the parallax in (3, III) is either trigonometric if available or derived from (8, III)) with C_v taken from Appendix B and constants from Baize and Romani (1946), then individual masses for A and B using (2, III) and then a new value of the parallax p from (13, III) which will replace the first parallax used in order to compute new values of absolute bolometric magnitudes for each star A and B, and so on, until stable values are obtained usually in less than 6 steps starting with the trigonometric parallax and nearly immediately with the dynamic parallax.

One can according to what is proposed by Mullaney (2005) do the same as above but initialize the process by choosing arbitrary initial masses equal to that of the Sun, i.e. 1, and $\Sigma m=2$, compute a first parallax using (13, III) that will be reused to compute absolute bolometric magnitudes for each star A and B using equation (3, III), then individual masses for A and B using (2, III) and then a new value of the parallax p from (13, III), and so on until one gets convergent values in less than 5 or 6 steps.

M_A	M_B	μ_A	μ_B	π	Σm	M_A	M_B	μ_A	μ_B	π	Σm
3,695	4,886	1,3185	0,9706	0,00570	2,29			1,000	1,000	0,00596	2,00
2,920	4,111	1,6094	1,1847	0,00533	2,79	3,018	4,209	1,569	1,155	0,00537	2,72
2,776	3,967	1,6702	1,2295	0,00526	2,90	2,794	3,985	1,662	1,224	0,00527	2,89
2,749	3,940	1,6818	1,2381	0,00525	2,92	2,752	3,943	1,680	1,237	0,00525	2,92
2,744	3,935	1,6840	1,2397	0,00525	2,92	2,744	3,935	1,684	1,239	0,00525	2,92
2,743	3,934	1,6844	1,2400	0,00525	2,92	2,743	3,934	1,684	1,240	0,00525	2,92
2,743	3,934	1,6845	1,2400	0,00525	2,92	2,743	3,934	1,684	1,240	0,00525	2,92
2,743	3,934	1,6845	1,2400	0,00525	2,92	2,743	3,934	1,684	1,240	0,00525	2,92
2,743	3,934	1,6845	1,2400	0,00525	2,92	2,743	3,934	1,684	1,240	0,00525	2,92
2,743	3,934	1,6845	1,2400	0,00525	2,92	2,743	3,934	1,684	1,240	0,00525	2,92
2,743	3,934	1,6845	1,2400	0,00525	2,92	2,743	3,934	1,684	1,240	0,00525	2,92

Table2: Example of convergence of M_A , M_B , μ_A , μ_B , π , Σm for HU 497 BC following the method described by the author i.e. left (starting with trigonometric parallax), or Mullaney (2005) right.

Trying to know the influence of a small variation of the factor k on the masses is interesting as k evolved from 0,1117 in (Couteau, 1978) to 0,0987 for (McAlister and Hartkopf, 1988) as was already mentioned. The spreadsheet has been programmed so that k is a parameter, the value of which can be easily changed. But let's try to assess the impact of factor k on the computation of the mass of A taking the partial derivative with respect to k of (9, III). First, $\log_{10} D$ will be replaced in (9, III) by the two first terms of its development in series near the origin:

$$\log_{10} D = \log_{10} 2 - \frac{k}{2} \cdot \Delta m \quad (14, III)$$

Hence:

$$\log_{10} \mu_A = (5k \cdot \log_{10} 2) / (3 - 5k) - (5k^2 \cdot \Delta m) / 2 \cdot (3 - 5k) - (3k / (3 - 5k)) \cdot \beta_A - (15k / (3 - 5k)) \cdot \log_{10} \alpha$$

let's now take the partial derivative with respect to k:

$$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k =$$

$$15 \log_{10} 2 / (3 - 5k)^2 - ((60-50k) \cdot k \cdot \Delta m) / 4(3 - 5k)^2 - 9 \beta_A / (3 - 5k)^2 - (45 \cdot \log_{10} \alpha) / (3 - 5k)^2$$

Thus:

$$\frac{\partial \log_{10} \mu_A}{\partial k} = \frac{15 \log_{10} 2 - \frac{(6-5k) 10 k \Delta m}{4} - 9 \beta_A - 45 \cdot \log_{10} \alpha}{(3-5k)^2} \quad (15, \text{III})$$

equation (15, III) can be re-arranged as:

$$\frac{\partial \log_{10} \mu_A}{\partial k} = \frac{5}{(3-5k)^2} \cdot [3 \log_{10} 2 - \frac{k(6-5k) \cdot \Delta m}{2} - \frac{9}{5} \beta_A - 9 \log_{10} \alpha] \quad (16, \text{III})^2$$

The lower the value of $\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$, the more the mass is independent of the value of k . It is asserted by Couteau (1978) that the variation of the mass is independent of k if (16,III) tends to zero and that this condition is close to be perfectly satisfied for binaries of spectral type G, and not far for most other types for which the residuals are small. Couteau (1978) asserts that the success of the method of dynamic parallaxes and masses is a result of that condition being satisfied and of a low dependency on small departures from the ML relation. The small sample we have in this paper shows that $\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$ does not necessarily tend to zero and that the dynamic parallaxes, but even more the masses, are somehow sensitive to k .

IV. Stellar evolution assessed with binaries' orbits

The Mass-Luminosity Relation used in (2, III) is somehow rough as it does not take into account the chemical composition of the stars, e.g. their metallicity, nor the slow but steady change of the kernel which leads to a slight but continuous increase in the stars' brightness with their age. In fact, this relation applies to what is referred to as the Zero Age (ZA), the time when the stars start having their nuclear reactions burning Hydrogen which corresponds to the Main Sequence (MS) and which lasts for 90% of the lifespan of the stars. Therefore, equation (2, III) is well suited as long as the system observed is not too old for having left the ZAMS. More generally, what we have presented in the previous section, which leads to dynamic parallaxes and masses, works well as long as the stars observed did not leave the ZAMS and does not suit very well the case of massive stars for which the evolution will be accelerated and the lifespan reduced. Couteau (1985, 1988, 1994) started promoting a fundamental relationship between the mass and the luminosity which applies to double stars having a known orbit and which does not make any hypothesis as in (2, III) nor requires the parallax. We start the reasoning with (5, III) and further define:

the ratio $R = \mu_B / \Sigma \mu$ and $\mu_A = (1 - R) \alpha^3 / p^3$ hence $p^3 = [(1 - R) \alpha^3] / \mu_A$ thus

$$3 \log_{10} p = \log_{10} ((1 - R) \alpha^3) - \log_{10} \mu_A \Rightarrow 3 \log_{10} p = \log_{10} (1 - R) + \log_{10} \alpha^3 - \log_{10} \mu_A$$

using (3, III) we have $\log_{10} p = (M_A - m_A - 5)/5$ and replacing p by its value:

$$3/5 M_A - 3/5 m_A - 3 = \log_{10} (1 - R) + 3 \log_{10} \alpha - \log_{10} \mu_A, \text{ hence multiplying by } 5/3$$

$$M_A - m_A - 5 = 5/3 \log_{10} (1 - R) + 5 \log_{10} \alpha - 5/3 \log_{10} \mu_A \text{ thus}$$

$$M_A = m_A + 5 + 5 \log_{10} \alpha + \frac{5}{3} \log_{10} (1 - R) - \frac{5}{3} \log_{10} \mu_A \quad (1, \text{IV})^3$$

Using the terminology adopted by Couteau (1994), the reduced absolute magnitude is noted M^* and knowing that:

² This equation is mistyped in Couteau (1978) eq (62,VI) p. 167

³ This equation is incorrect in Couteau (1988), eq (10,XI) p. 221

$$M^*_A = M_A + \frac{5}{3} \log_{10} \mu_A \quad (2, IV)$$

one can infer replacing M_A by its value (1, IV) that:

$$M^*_A = m_A + 5 + 5 \log_{10} \alpha + \frac{5}{3} \log_{10} (1 - R) \quad (3, IV)^4$$

The nice property of equation (3, IV) is that the reduced absolute magnitude depends only on the apparent magnitude (measured in a photometric system), the orbital constant α , and the mass ratio R . There is no hypothesis or need of an empirical relationship as the MLR in (2, III), and (3, IV) is based on fundamental data, except R which varies only slightly between 0,45 and 0,5 and has a limited effect through its logarithm. Exactly in the same way as one can obtain bolometric magnitude M , applying the bolometric correction C_{vb} to the visual magnitude $M = V + C_{vb}$, we have for the reduced magnitudes $M^* = V^* + C_{vb}$, with C_{vb} from (Harris et al., 1963) or:

$$V^* = M^* - C_{vb} \quad (4a, IV)$$

or:

$$V^* = V + \frac{5}{3} \log_{10} \mu \quad (4b, IV)$$

with V the visual absolute magnitude according to Rakos (1984) or

$$V = V^* - \frac{5}{3} \log_{10} \mu \quad (4c, IV)$$

that we can use to compute the parallax with:

$$\log_{10} p = \frac{(V_A - m_A)}{5} - 1 \quad (5, IV)$$

The diagram (B-V), M^* or (B-V), V^* applied to double stars, where (B-V) are color indices linked to the spectral type, gives information on the luminosity of the stars, without knowing their parallax which, notwithstanding its ignorance, fully plays its role throughout the orbital constant α . We will refer to it as CHR-diagram, for Couteau-Hertzprung-Russell as it shares its main properties with the original HR-diagram, except that no need of the trigonometric parallax is required and therefore no assumption is made with respect to the absolute magnitude of the stars. Couteau (1994) applied this approach to thirty primary components of COU double stars and could already identify on this small sample very clearly three spectral classes, i.e. giants (sub-giants of class IV and some probable class III), main sequence V, and sub-dwarfs (class VI). The great value of this CHR-diagram is to sort out double stars according to their spectral type and therefore limit the usage of dynamic parallaxes and masses to those falling into the main sequence part.

Using (2, III) with $k=0,0987$ (McAlister and Hartkopf, 1988) and (2, IV) one can get the flow equation from the reduced absolute magnitudes to the absolute magnitudes:

$$M_A = M^*_A + (5k/3) M_A - (5k/3) \cdot 4,77 \text{ hence } M_A (1 - (5k/3)) = M^*_A - 0,7846 \text{ then}$$

$$0,8355 M_A = M^*_A - 0,7846 \text{ thus}$$

$$M_A = 1,1968 M^*_A - 0,9390 \quad (6, IV)$$

Extracting M_A from (2, IV), i.e. $M_A = M^*_A - (5/3) \log_{10} \mu_A$ and replacing in (2, III) M_A by its value as defined in (2, IV) we will obtain a new relation of Zero Age between the mass and the reduced absolute magnitude:

⁴ There is a typesetting error with a – instead of a + in this equation in Couteau (1994).

$\log_{10} \mu_A = -k M_A^* + 5k/3 \log_{10} \mu_A + k M_\odot$ thus:

$\log_{10} \mu_A - 5k/3 \log_{10} \mu_A = -k M_A^* + k M_\odot$ hence:

$(1-5k/3) \log_{10} \mu_A = -k M_A^* + k M_\odot$ therefore:

$$\log_{10} \mu_A = \frac{-k M_A^* + M_\odot}{1 - \frac{5k}{3}} \quad (7, IV)$$

and again replacing k by its value, i.e. 0,0987, though k is a parameter in the spreadsheet (Poyet, 2017) to enable sensitivity studies, we get:

$\log_{10} \mu_A = -(0,0987/0,8355) M_A^* + (0,0987/0,8355) M_\odot$, hence with the absolute magnitude of the sun $M_\odot=4,77$ we get:

$$\log_{10} \mu_A = -0,1181 M_A^* + 0,5634$$

The strength of (7, IV) is that M_A^* is known precisely from (3, IV) and in this new relation, the parallax, be it known or not, plays its role through the orbital constant α . The mass which is calculated in that manner supposes that the star is still in its ZAMS stage. To confirm it, one just needs to see whether the mass matches what one can expect from its spectral type, or (B-V) as given in Appendix F. If it does not, it means that the star has evolved, is not “zero age” any longer and has left the main sequence, and its brilliance is over-luminous and can be evaluated. One just needs to assign to the star a mass corresponding to its (B-V) in Appendix F, then using (2, IV) one gets a visual absolute magnitude, the difference of which with the zero age value gives an indicator of evolution.

A more representative CHR-diagram is provided in (Couteau, 1988), where 150 double stars having trustworthy orbits have been used, provided that measures of their (B-V) was available. Abscissa is (B-V) which has the advantage to be a measure as opposed to the spectral type which is a classification (or a temperature which remains somehow arbitrary) and ordinate is V^* . This is a fundamental diagram as the position of the stars does not depend on any hypothesis or measure of parallax (and few could have been plotted in a HR-diagram as the absolute magnitude requires the parallax). This representation shows the grouping around the ZAMS, and few stars fall below as they are sub-dwarfs, but a number of them lie above the ZAMS, some being very remote and correspond to old stars getting more and more luminous as their photosphere grows. The knowledge of V^* at the same time as one computes the orbit enables to position of the star on the CHR-diagram and to determine at once if the object is of zero age and if one can reliably apply to it the computation of dynamic parallax and masses.

V. Visual Binaries Studied

RST 3340

WDS 00055-1835, BD -19,8447, 10.4-10.4, Sp G3V, PM +004+005. This is a southern object as the declination makes the binary extremely difficult for northern observers given the close separation. 8 observations have been used to compute the orbit, starting with the first observation and discovery by Rossiter, R.A. in 1935,706, and last by Mason *et al.* (2011) on 2001,5701. Unfortunately we do not know the trigonometric parallax. Given the observations, one could easily draw three competing ellipses having one of the foci (West) slightly shifted to the South.

spectral type G3 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman (1959), i.e. $0,99\mu_{\odot}$. As the trigonometric parallax is not available, one cannot compute $\Sigma\mu$ (1, III). Masses computed with the dynamic parallax without or with the convergence algorithm match very well. The mass computed with (9, III), i.e. $1,01\mu_{\odot}$ or (7,IV), i.e. $0,9\mu_{\odot}$ also corresponds well to that found in the Appendix F for Sp=G3, i.e. $0,97\mu_{\odot}$. Note that $\partial\log_{10}\mu_A/\partial k$ is minimum for this spectral type and class.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – RST 3340							
V_{Mag}	10,08	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-2,0586	π dyn lter/Conv.	0,00900	P prob (13,III)	153,14
(B-V) color idx	0,560	π (dyn)	0,00874	μ_A by lter/Conv.	0,93	M^* (3,IV)	5,18
m_A	10,40	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,00622	μ_B by lter/Conv.	0,93	V^* (4a, IV)	5,26
m_B	10,40	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,01	Σm by lter/Conv.	1,86	μ_A from (7,IV)	0,90
Sp	G3V	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	-0,03159	d parsec	111,17	V_A (4c, IV)	5,34
Cv_A	-0,08	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	0,93	d light years	362,59	π from (5,IV)	0,00971
π trigo (mas)	N/A	$\mu_A \pi_{dyn} + \mu_B \pi_{dyn}$	1,94	a UA	32,41	CHR diagram	" \approx -" ZAMS
$\Sigma\mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	N/A	$\Sigma\mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	2,03	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial\log_{10}\mu_A/\partial k$	0,08

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $9,222\text{mas} \pm 0,684$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{dyn}} = 1,944\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,085$, $\mu_{A\pi_{dyn}} = 0,947 \pm 0,061$, $\mu_{B\pi_{dyn}} = 0,930 \pm 0,034$.

HU 616

WDS 06541+3341, BD 33,1427, ADS 5544, HIP 33145, apparent magnitudes 10.0-10.4, Sp F0, PM -008-016. No orbit is listed by (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017). Only 5 observations have been used to compute the orbit, but they are well distributed along the trajectory of the companion, starting with the first observation and discovery by Hussey W. J. in 1902,76, and last by R. Gili on 1990,148.

HU 616 apparent ellipse, drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 405,55mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

Equation (13, III) gives a probable period at discovery of 128,01, which is a reasonable preliminary estimate for the real computed period of 181,27. The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – HU 616			
P=181,27	a"=0,155	A"=-0,0925	C"= 0,1139
n=1,98599	i°=54,03	B"=0,0493	H"= 0,0521
T=2011,11	Ω°=99,85	F"=-0,0132	F1"= -0,0123
e=0,356	ω°=65,41	G"=-0,1451	G1"= -0,1356

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

HU 616 - HIP 33145 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,5	191,40	0,06
2018,5	198,44	0,06
2019,5	205,20	0,06
2020,5	211,57	0,07
2021,5	217,49	0,07
2022,5	222,92	0,07
2023,5	227,87	0,07
2024,5	232,37	0,08
2025,5	236,46	0,08
2026,5	240,16	0,09

Spectral type F0V and the position occupied by the star on the CHR diagram (0,230 – 3,13) confirms its class V status and falls perfectly on the ZAMS line. Mass of A as computed from (7,IV) matches perfectly that estimated according spectral type F0 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman (1959), i.e. $1,58\mu_{\odot}$. Masses computed with (9,III) and (10, III) seem a bit over-rated, whereas dynamic results, i.e. the dynamic parallax and masses computed with the convergence algorithm or without (7,IV) are close at around $\mu_A \approx 1,64\mu_{\odot}$ which is slightly above that found in the Appendix F for Sp=F8, i.e. $1,49\mu_{\odot}$.

The former trigonometric parallax $3,5 \pm 1,3$ seemed to slightly under-evaluate the distance and leads to slightly under-estimated Σ masses (1, III), though the parallax computed with (5, IV) is very close to this trigonometric value. Overall all dynamic results are in close accordance and show little deviations. Latest trigonometric parallax values from “Gaia” as published by (Brown et al., 2016) and accessed through SIMBAD give a trigonometric parallax of $2,57 \pm 0,61$, which gives a value of $\Sigma\mu = 6,65\mu_{\odot}$ with (1,III) in the very wide range of $[3,51-14,98]\mu_{\odot}$ and seems this time to over-estimate the sum of the masses, though our value based on the dynamic parallax (1, III) at 3,84 still falls within the new range.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – HU 616							
V_{Mag}	9,34	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-2,5105	π dyn Iter/Conv.	0,00328	P prob (13,III)	128,01
(B-V) color idx	0,230	π (dyn)	0,00309	μ_A by Iter/Conv.	1,68	M^* (3,IV)	3,05
m_A	10,00	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,30229	μ_B by Iter/Conv.	1,53	V^* (4a, IV)	3,13
m_B	10,40	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	2,01	Σm by Iter/Conv.	3,21	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,60
Sp	F0V	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	0,18484	d parsec	305,18	V_A (4c, IV)	2,79
Cv_A	-0,08	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	1,53	d light years	995,37	π from (5,IV)	0,00362
π trigo (mas)	2,57	$\mu_A \pi_{dyn} + \mu_B \pi_{dyn}$	3,54	a UA	50,14	CHR diagram	"=" ZAMS
$\Sigma\mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	6,65	$\Sigma\mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	3,84	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	3,63

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $3,354 \text{mas} \pm 0,378$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{dyn}} = 3,527\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,315$, $\mu_{A\pi_{dyn}} = 1,759 \pm 0,217$, $\mu_{B\pi_{dyn}} = 1,531 \pm 0,119$.

HU 841

WDS 07400+6603, BD 66,518, ADS 6228, HIP 37353, apparent magnitudes 9.4-9.4, Sp G, PM -005-022. No orbit is listed by (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017). 15 observations have been used to compute the orbit, starting with the first observation and discovery by Hussey W. J. in 1904,94, and last by Heintz, W.D. on 1986,17. No more recent observation is available.

HU 841 apparent ellipse, drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 257,81mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

Equation (13, III) gives a probable period at discovery of 97,17, which is a reasonable preliminary estimate for the real computed period of 155,58. The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – HU 841			
P=155,58	a"=0,253	A"=0,1435	C"= -0,1780
n=2,31392	i°=50,28	B"=-0,1086	H"= -0,0788
T=2010,24	Ω °=87,60	F"=0,0751	F1"= 0,0465
e=0,785	ω °=246,11	G"=0,2285	G1"= 0,1416

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

HU 841 - HIP 37353 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,5	254,10	0,10
2018,5	259,21	0,11
2019,5	263,41	0,13
2020,5	266,95	0,14
2021,5	269,99	0,15
2022,5	272,64	0,16
2023,5	274,97	0,18
2024,5	277,04	0,19
2025,5	278,91	0,20
2026,5	280,60	0,20

Spectral type F8V and the position occupied by the star on the CHR diagram (0,345 – 3,61)

confirms its class V status though it lies slightly above the ZAMS line. Mass of A is above that estimated according to spectral type F8 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman, (1959), i.e. $1,19\mu_{\odot}$. All dynamic results, the dynamic parallax and masses computed without or with the convergence algorithm match very well. The mass computed with (9, III) or (7,IV) is above that found in the Appendix F for $Sp=F8$, i.e. $1,13\mu_{\odot}$. The trigonometric parallax $7,54\pm 1,44$ seems to under-evaluate the distance and leads to under-estimated Σ masses (1, III), but with a wide range $\Sigma\mu[0,93-2,95]\mu_{\odot}$ given the $\pm 1,44$ uncertainty on the value of the trigonometric parallax. Σ masses determined by iteration/convergence at $2,80\mu_{\odot}$ falls within that range.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – HU 841							
V_{Mag}	8,95	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-2,2248	π dyn lter/Conv.	0,00621	P prob (13,III)	97,17
(B-V) color idx	0,490	π (dyn)	0,00596	μ_A by lter/Conv.	1,40	M^* (3,IV)	3,69
m_A	9,40	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,19979	μ_B by lter/Conv.	1,40	V^* (4a, IV)	3,77
m_B	9,40	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,58	Σm by lter/Conv.	2,80	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,34
Sp	F8V	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	0,14663	d parsec	161,11	V_A (4c, IV)	3,55
C_{V_A}	-0,08	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	1,40	d light years	525,47	π from (5,IV)	0,00678
π trigo (mas)	7,54	$\mu_A \pi \text{dyn} + \mu_B \pi \text{dyn}$	2,99	a UA	42,49	CHR diagram	"+" ZAMS
$\Sigma\mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	1,56	$\Sigma\mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	3,17	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	2,42

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $6,367\text{mas} \pm 0,577$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{dyn}}=2,986\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,183$, $\mu_{A\pi_{dyn}}=1,443\pm 0,126$, $\mu_{B\pi_{dyn}}=1,402\pm 0,071$.

A 552

WDS 08441-0412, BD -03,2454, ADS 6964, HIP 42863, apparent magnitudes 7.55-9.37, Sp A2, PM -019+002. 10 observations from the discovery date by Aitken in 1903,04 to last interferometric measures by Hartkopf, W.I. in 1996,8666. I found it very surprising that no orbit had yet been computed as the companion seems to have made a complete rotation since the discovery. No orbit is listed by (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017). This star is the typical example for which successive orbits, more elliptic each time, had to be envisaged until the law of areas could be better satisfied. The final ellipse proposed is quite far from the initial attempts. It is a preliminary orbit.

A 552 apparent ellipse, drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 362,50. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

Equation (13, III) gives a probable period at discovery of 91,32, which is a good preliminary estimate for the real computed period of 106,58. The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – A 552			
P=106,58	a"=0,197	A"=-0,1186	C"= 0,0071
n=3,37774	i°=60,13	B"=-0,1572	H"= -0,1708
T=1957,40	Ω°=54,15	F"=0,0747	F1"= 0,0676
e=0,427	ω°=177,63	G"=-0,0640	G1"= -0,0579

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

A 552 - HIP 42863 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,5	57,73	0,28
2018,5	58,51	0,27
2019,5	59,29	0,27
2020,5	60,09	0,27
2021,5	60,91	0,27
2022,5	61,74	0,26
2023,5	62,59	0,26
2024,5	63,46	0,26
2025,5	64,36	0,25
2026,5	65,29	0,25

Spectral type A2V and the position occupied by the star on the CHR diagram (0,170 – 2,18) confirms its class V status as it lies very close to the ZAMS line. Mass of A is in good accordance with spectral type A2 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman (1959), i.e. 2,50μ_⊙. All dynamic results, the dynamic parallax and masses computed without or with the convergence algorithm match well. The mass computed with (7,IV) matches perfectly that found in the Appendix F for Sp=F8, i.e. 2,19μ_⊙. The trigonometric parallax 5,69±0,93 gives very comparable results, i.e. Σμ_{π-trigo}=3,66μ_⊙ to those obtained by iteration/convergence, i.e. Σμ_{iter/conv}=3,88μ_⊙. Obviously, ∂log₁₀μ_A/∂k increases for this spectral type.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – A 552

V _{Mag}	7,30	log π (8,III)	-2,2634	π dyn lter/Conv.	0,00558	P prob (13,III)	91,32
(B-V) color idx	0,170	π (dyn)	0,00545	μ _A by lter/Conv.	2,34	M* (3,IV)	1,93
m _A	7,55	log μ _A (9, III)	0,39846	μ _B by lter/Conv.	1,55	V* (4a, IV)	2,18
m _B	9,37	μ _A π dyn	2,50	Σμ by lter/Conv.	3,88	μ _A from (7,IV)	2,17
Sp	A2V	log μ _B (10, III)	0,18929	d parsec	179,29	V _A (4c, IV)	1,62
CV _A	-0,25	μ _B π dyn	1,55	d light years	584,78	π from (5,IV)	0,00651
π trigo (mas)	5,69	μ _A πdyn+μ _B πdyn	4,05	a UA	36,15	CHR diagram "≈" ZAMS	
Σμ π trigo (1,III)	3,66	Σμ π dyn (1,III)	4,16	k (MLR)	0,0987	∂log ₁₀ μ _A /∂k	4,63

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of 5,982mas ±0,749, Σμ_{(A+B)πdyn}=4,031μ_⊙ ±0,138, μ_{Aπdyn}=2,336±0,168, μ_{Bπdyn}=1,546±0,074.

A 2554

WDS 08539+0149, BD 02,2088, ADS 7074, HIP 43676, apparent magnitudes 7.44-9.64, Sp F0, PM +010-040. There are two orbits, one by Zirm, H. (Zir2007) with $P=83,6y$, the other by Tokovinin, A. (Tok2015c) with $P=43,86y$. To be honest, the data plot used by Zirm wds08539+0149a.png is easily recognizable even though we made slightly different choices with respect to the foci, whereas the one by Tokovinin, i.e. wds08539+0149o.png cannot be matched with the one we produce with the 16 observations we have.

A 2554 apparent ellipse, drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 212,50mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

Equation (13, III) gives a probable period at discovery of 93,26, which is a good guess for the real computed period of 82,60. Take note that motion of the companion is retrograde, i.e. θ goes descending. The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – A 2554			
P=82,60	$a''=0,359$	$A''=0,0706$	$C''= -0,2740$
$n=4,35835$	$i''=126,24$	$B''=0,2212$	$H''= 0,0939$
T=1980,5	$\Omega''=12,41$	$F''=0,3466$	$F1''= 0,2824$
$e=0,580$	$\omega''=288,92$	$G''=0,0058$	$G1''= 0,0047$

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

A 2554 - HIP 43676 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017	262,65	0,35
2018	260,35	0,35
2019	258,10	0,35
2020	255,90	0,36
2021	253,76	0,36
2022	251,66	0,37
2023	249,61	0,37
2024	247,62	0,38
2025	245,68	0,38
2026	243,78	0,38

Spectral type A9V and the position occupied by the star on the CHR diagram (0,345 – 3,61) confirms its class V status. Mass of A is in accordance with spectral type A9 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman (1959), i.e. $1,62\mu_{\odot}$. All results either computed with the trigonometric parallax or with the dynamic parallax without or with the convergence algorithm match very well. The mass computed with (9, III) or (7,IV) also corresponds well to that found in the Appendix F for Sp=A9, i.e. $1,57\mu_{\odot}$. The trigonometric parallax $14,79\pm 1,02$ gives a range of $\Sigma\mu[1,72-2,60]\mu_{\odot}$ given the $\pm 1,02$ uncertainty within which all dynamic values fall easily.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – A 2554

V_{Mag}	7,23	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-1,8542	π dyn lter/Conv.	0,01426	P prob (13,III)	93,26
(B-V) color idx	0,345	π (dyn)	0,01399	μ_A by lter/Conv.	1,46	M^* (3,IV)	3,51
m_A	7,44	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,18862	μ_B by lter/Conv.	0,88	V^* (4a, IV)	3,61
m_B	9,64	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,54	Σm by lter/Conv.	2,34	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,41
Sp	A9V	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	-0,05333	d parsec	70,13	V_A (4c, IV)	3,36
Cv_A	-0,10	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	0,88	d light years	228,75	π from (5,IV)	0,01527
π trigo (mas)	14,8	$\mu_A \pi_{dyn} + \mu_B \pi_{dyn}$	2,43	a UA	25,67	CHR diagram	"=" ZAMS
$\Sigma\mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	2,10	$\Sigma\mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	2,48	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	2,04

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $14,628\text{mas} \pm 0,903$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{dyn}} = 2,417\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,070$, $\mu_{A\pi_{dyn}} = 1,471 \pm 0,068$, $\mu_{B\pi_{dyn}} = 0,884 \pm 0,031$. Finally the solution proposed with $P=82,6\text{y}$ is way closer to the one from Zirm even though the orientation of the orbit differs significantly. 16 observations have been used to compute the orbit, starting with the first observation and discovery by R. G. Aitken in 1913,11, and last on 1996,8665 by W.I. Hartkopf.

BU 796

WDS 12175+0636, BD 07,2529, ADS 8500, HIP 59916, apparent magnitudes 8.38-9.46, Sp F2, PM +027-040. No orbit is listed by (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017). 34 observations have been used to compute the orbit, starting with the first observation and discovery by W. Burnham in 1881,34, and last on 1989,28 by W. D. Heintz. This system is somehow frustrating as it has been measured for more than a century by the best observers using the largest instruments of their time and the measures look like a very heterogeneously scattered plot, showing an odd disposition, but does not resemble a drift due to proper motion. So we clearly have an orbital system, but the tentative orbit proposed, which should probably be even more elliptical, has just the objective to draw the attention on this star, and is a very preliminary attempt. The situation might be more complex and a third companion, or more, could disturb the trajectories (or else ?), and the discussion is open and criticisms welcome.

BU 796 apparent ellipse drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 208,33mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – BU 796			
P=110,26	a"=0,414	A"=0,0192	C"= 0,1651
n=3,26501	i°=69,97	B"=0,3792	H"= 0,3522
T=1966,70	Ω°=77,98	F"=-0,1622	F1"= -0,1368
e=0,538	ω°=25,12	G"=-0,1452	G1"= -0,1224

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

BU 796 - HIP 59916 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,0	264,87	0,60
2018,0	265,32	0,60
2019,0	265,78	0,60
2020,0	266,24	0,59
2021,0	266,71	0,59
2022,0	267,18	0,58
2023,0	267,67	0,58
2024,0	268,16	0,57
2025,0	268,66	0,57
2026,0	269,17	0,56

All results are summarized in the following table. Spectral type F2 and class V is confirmed by the position occupied on the CHR diagram (0,400 – 4,35), though the star lies slightly below the ZAMS. Mass of A computed with (9, III), $1,33 \mu_{\odot}$, is in reasonable accordance with spectral type A5 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman (1959), i.e. $1,46 \mu_{\odot}$. The trigonometric parallax as given by SIMBAD $7,21 \pm 0,45 \text{mas}$ gives extremely dubious results, i.e. $\Sigma \mu = 15,58 \mu_{\odot}$ (1, III), very far from dynamic calculations and common sense as two massive B7 stars (which is not the case) will hardly go further than $7,68 \mu_{\odot}$ (Appendix F). Results offered by (8, III), (9, III), (10, III), (1, III) with dynamic parallax, parallax and masses obtained by iteration / convergence and finally (7, IV) are very consistent. Finally, $\mu_{A \pi \text{dyn}}$ is just slightly under that found in the Appendix F, i.e. $1,38 \mu_{\odot}$, for Sp=F2.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – BU 796							
V _{Mag}	7,92	log π (8,III)	-1,8692	π dyn lter/Conv.	0,01409	P prob (13,III)	172,40
(B-V) color idx	0,400	π (dyn)	0,01351	μ _A by lter/Conv.	1,17	M* (3,IV)	4,30
m _A	8,38	log μ _A (9, III)	0,12299	μ _B by lter/Conv.	0,92	V* (4a, IV)	4,35
m _B	9,46	μ _A π dyn	1,33	Σm by lter/Conv.	2,09	μ _A from (7,IV)	1,14
Sp	F2V	log μ _B (10, III)	-0,03794	d parsec	70,98	V _A (4c, IV)	4,26
Cv _A	-0,05	μ _B π dyn	0,92	d light years	231,49	π from (5,IV)	0,01500
π trigo (mas)	7,21	μ _A π _{dyn} +μ _B π _{dyn}	2,24	a UA	30,64	CHR diagram	"-" ZAMS
Σμ π trigo (1,III)	15,58	Σμ π dyn (1,III)	2,37	k (MLR)	0,0987	∂log ₁₀ μ _A /∂k	1,38

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $14,257 \text{mas} \pm 1,051$, $\Sigma \mu_{(A+B) \pi \text{dyn}} = 2,232 \mu_{\odot} \pm 0,139$, $\mu_{A \pi \text{dyn}} = 1,211 \pm 0,102$, $\mu_{B \pi \text{dyn}} = 0,916 \pm 0,052$.

RST 4502

WDS 12349-0509, BD -04,3307, apparent magnitudes 8.49-9.34, Sp A5, PM -030-005. No orbit is listed by (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017). 18 observations have been used to compute the orbit, starting with the first observation and discovery by R.A. Rossiter in 1938,475, and last on 1997,1317 by W.I. Hartkopf.

RST 4502 apparent ellipse drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 397,62mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – RST 4502			
P=147,54	a''=0,172	A''=0,0126	C''= 0,0718
n=2,44002	i°=50,70	B''=-0,1559	H''= 0,1122
T=2029,46	Ω °=72,56	F''=0,1154	F1''= 0,1119
e=0,244	ω °=32,60	G''=0,0609	G1''= 0,0591

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

RST 4502 - BD -04,3307 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,5	264,33	0,13
2018,5	267,13	0,12
2019,5	270,03	0,12
2020,5	273,05	0,12
2021,5	276,21	0,12
2022,5	279,53	0,11
2023,5	283,03	0,11
2024,5	286,73	0,11
2025,5	290,64	0,10
2026,5	294,77	0,10

All results are summarized in the following table. Spectral type A5 and class V is confirmed by the position occupied on the CHR diagram (0,260 – 2,22), though the star lies slightly above the ZAMS. Mass of A computed with (7, IV), $2,08 \mu_{\odot}$, is in good accordance with spectral type A5 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman (1959), i.e. $1,94 \mu_{\odot}$. The trigonometric parallax $3,76 \pm 0,61 \text{mas}$ gives results, i.e. $\Sigma\mu=4,41 \mu_{\odot}$ (I, III), close to what is obtained by dynamic

calculations, i.e. $\Sigma\mu=4,33 \mu_{\odot}$. Results offered by (8, III), (9, III), (10, III), (1, III) with dynamic parallax, parallax and masses obtained by iteration / convergence and finally (7, IV) are very consistent. Finally, the mass computed by dynamic means is just slightly above that found in the Appendix F for Sp=A5, i.e. $1,90 \mu_{\odot}$.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – RST 4502							
V_{Mag}	8,02	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-2,4305	π dyn Iter/Conv.	0,00387	P prob (13,III)	86,76
(B-V) color idx	0,260	π (dyn)	0,00371	μ_A by Iter/Conv.	2,21	M^* (3,IV)	2,07
m_A	8,49	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,39998	μ_B by Iter/Conv.	1,82	V^* (4a, IV)	2,22
m_B	9,34	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	2,51	Σm by Iter/Conv.	4,03	μ_A from (7,IV)	2,08
Sp	A5	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	0,26056	d parsec	258,22	V_A (4c, IV)	1,69
Cv_A	-0,15	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	1,82	d light years	842,21	π from (5,IV)	0,00437
π trigo (mas)	3,76	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn + $\mu_B \pi$ dyn	4,33	a UA	46,38	CHR diagram "+" ZAMS	
$\Sigma\mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	4,41	$\Sigma\mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	4,58	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	4,76

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $4,039\text{mas} \pm 0,464$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{dyn}}=4,316\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,275$, $\mu_{A\pi_{dyn}}=2,268 \pm 0,220$, $\mu_{B\pi_{dyn}}=1,822 \pm 0,113$.

A 1097 AB

WDS 14020+5713, BD 57,1478, ADS 9089, HIP 68554, apparent magnitudes 7,76-8.24, Sp F5, PM -008-011. There have been three orbits published for this system, i.e. Cou1960c (P=126y), Inv1960 (P=333,3y), Sca2000a (P=224,7y). With a period of 144,81y the solution we propose differs significantly from the one from Scardia (2000) and is closer to that of Couteau (1960), though observations have since elongated much the ellipse towards the West (last observation used by Couteau was in 1959,44). 58 observations have been used to compute the orbit, starting with the first observation and discovery by Aitken R. G., in 1905,77, and last on 2000,49 by Docobo, J.A. The final observation listed in the WDS (2010) fits well in the plot.

A 1097 AB apparent ellipse drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 202,76mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – A 1097 AB			
P=144,81	a"=0,394	A"=0,2318	C"= -0,3019
n=2,48602	i°=53,92	B"=0,1036	H"= 0,1024
T=1894,5	Ω°=84,15	F"=-0,0361	F1"= -0,0345
e=0,294	ω°=288,73	G"=0,3793	G1"= 0,3625

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

A 1097 AB - HIP 68554 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017	276,41	0,34
2018	278,31	0,33
2019	280,33	0,32
2020	282,47	0,31
2021	284,76	0,30
2022	287,22	0,29
2023	289,87	0,28
2024	292,76	0,27
2025	295,91	0,26
2026	299,37	0,24

All results are summarized in the following table. Spectral type F5 and class V is confirmed by the position occupied on the CHR diagram (0,461 – 3,96). Mass of A is in good accordance with spectral type F5 as given for the main sequence by Pecker and Schatzman (1959), i.e. 1,35 μ_{\odot} . The trigonometric parallax 6,82±0,69mas seems under-estimated and gives results far from the well grouped and consistent results offered by (8, III), (9, III), (10, III), (1, III) with the dynamic parallax, or parallax and masses obtained by iteration / convergence and finally (7, IV). The mass computed with by iteration / convergence or (7, IV) corresponds well to that found in the Appendix F for Sp=F5, i.e. 1,25 μ_{\odot} . $\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$ is rather small for this spectral type and class (the star falls nearly on the ZAMS line in CHR diagram), hence the MLR is well obeyed which comforts the dynamic results.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – 1097 AB							
V_{Mag}	7,80	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-2,0069	π dyn Iter/Conv.	0,01049	P prob (13,III)	142,29
(B-V) color idx	0,461	π (dyn)	0,00984	μ_A by Iter/Conv.	1,31	M* (3,IV)	3,92
m_A	8,51	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,20177	μ_B by Iter/Conv.	1,22	V* (4a, IV)	3,96
m_B	8,83	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,59	Σm by Iter/Conv.	2,53	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,26
Sp	F5	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	0,08641	d parsec	95,30	V_A (4c, IV)	3,79
Cv_A	-0,04	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	1,22	d light years	310,82	π from (5,IV)	0,01139
π trigo (mas)	6,82	$\mu_A \pi \text{dyn} + \mu_B \pi \text{dyn}$	2,81	a UA	40,08	CHR diagram	"≈" ZAMS
$\Sigma \mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	9,23	$\Sigma \mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	3,07	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	2,41

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of 10,617mas ±1,093, $\Sigma \mu_{(A+B)\pi_{dyn}}=2,805\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,268$, $\mu_{A\pi_{dyn}}=1,389 \pm 0,177$, $\mu_{B\pi_{dyn}}=1,220 \pm 0,099$.

HU 337

WDS 19188+1736, BD 17,3924, ADS 12301, HIP 94911, apparent magnitudes 9.27-10.14, Sp A3, PM -005+007. No orbit is listed by (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017). 16 observations have been used to

compute the orbit, starting with the first observation and discovery by Hussey W. J. in 1901,51, and last on 1989,69 by Le Beau, J. Three observations from Van Biesbroeck are dubious with respect to the separation namely VBS 1951,816, 1954,05, 1954,8 and are given at 0,"09. VBS 1951,816 is reported by the author himself has having an uncertain position angle. Notice should be taken that measures made at Mac Donald (T200) by Van Biesbroeck were systematically too short in separation as reported by Couteau (1988) in comparative Table (3, VIII), p.127.

Close to the minimum separation, we have two measures from Van den Bos with the T200 at Mac Donald 1958,65 (0,"12) and 1961,69 (0,"10) even though Couteau (1988) states that Van den Bos was reluctant to measure down to that limit. Couteau (1988) also reminds that Van den Bos was probably the greatest double stars observer of all times. We also have one measure by Couteau 1970,48 (336°,0,"11) with the 74cm refractor in Nice, that he evaluates as uncertain, but which appears to be magic work, right on spot.

HU 337 apparent ellipse drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 303,70mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – HU 337			
P=228,90	a"=0,234	A"=0,0395	C"= 0,1584
n=1,57276	i°=126,32	B"=-0,1679	H"= -0,1026
T=1989,1	Ω °=60,78	F"=-0,1618	F1"= -0,1581
e=0,213	ω °=122,92	G"=-0,1348	G1"= -0,1317

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

HU 337 - HIP 94911 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,5	235,89	0,20
2018,5	234,69	0,20
2019,5	233,50	0,20
2020,5	232,31	0,20
2021,5	231,13	0,20
2022,5	229,94	0,20
2023,5	228,75	0,20
2024,5	227,57	0,20
2025,5	226,37	0,20
2026,5	225,18	0,20

All results are summarized in the following table. Spectral type A3 and class V is confirmed by the

position occupied on the CHR diagram (0,310 – 3,09), though the star lies slightly above the main sequence and probably shows a beginning of evolution from the ZAMS. In any case, mass of A is in reasonable accordance with spectral type A3 as given for the main sequence by (Pecker and Schatzman, 1959), i.e. $1,70\mu_{\odot}$. The mass computed with (9, III), i.e. 2,05, matches very well the value found in Appendix F for Sp=A3. Latest value of trigonometric parallax (SIMBAD), i.e. $4,15\pm 1,18\text{mas}$ ($\pm 14,22\%$ error), leads to a very wide a range of $\Sigma\mu_{\text{trigo}}[1,62-9,32]\mu_{\odot}$ at a 68,2% confidence interval, therefore dynamic results are well within that range.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – HU 337

V_{Mag}	8,79	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-2,3938	π dyn lter/Conv.	0,00422	P prob (13,III)	304,65
(B-V) color idx	0,310	π (dyn)	0,00404	μ_A by lter/Conv.	1,80	M^* (3,IV)	2,89
m_A	9,27	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,31082	μ_B by lter/Conv.	1,47	V^* (4a, IV)	3,09
m_B	10,14	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	2,05	Σm by lter/Conv.	3,27	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,67
Sp	A3	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	0,16825	d parsec	237,10	V_A (4c, IV)	2,72
Cv_A	-0,20	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	1,47	d light years	773,31	π from (5,IV)	0,00489
π trigo (mas)	4,15	$\mu_A \pi_{\text{dyn}} + \mu_B \pi_{\text{dyn}}$	3,52	a UA	58,00	CHR diagram	" \approx " ZAMS
$\Sigma\mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	3,43	$\Sigma\mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	3,72	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	3,68

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $4,465\text{mas} \pm 0,604$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{\text{dyn}}} = 3,504\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,228$, $\mu_{A\pi_{\text{dyn}}} = 1,836 \pm 0,192$, $\mu_{B\pi_{\text{dyn}}} = 1,473 \pm 0,097$. Having partially recounted the history of the measures on HU 337, the trajectory seems long and well shaped enough to compute a preliminary orbit, but the star moves to its new separation maximum around 0,"20 during the period (2017-2027) and CCD/EMCCD or speckle observations would enable to get better elements.

HO 137

WDS 20406+2948, BD 29,4131, ADS 14149, HIP 102033, apparent magnitudes 6.13-9.26, Sp A2V, PM +020+046. No orbit is listed by (Hartkopf and Mason, 2017).

HO 137 apparent ellipse drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 92,34mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

26 observations have been used to compute the orbit above, starting with the discovery and first observation by G.W. Hough in 1885,83, and last on 2007,7918, θ : 351°,8, ρ :0",74, i.e. unpublished measure with a filar micrometer by the author with a T40,6 Cassegrain reflector (F/D=26,87) with a flat supporting the hyperbolic (Poyet, 2014).

The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – HO 137			
P=258,26	a"=1,202	A"=-0,0542	C"= 1,0426
n=1,39394	i°=61,61	B"=0,5963	H"= 0,2290
T=2041,00	Ω °=30,72	F"=-1,0702	F1"= -0,6993
e=0,757	ω °=77,61	G"=-0,4978	G1"= -0,3252

This orbit is pretty odd and should be considered as very preliminary, time will tell. The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

HO 137 - HIP 102033 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,0	3,54	0,69
2018,0	5,01	0,68
2019,0	6,52	0,67
2020,0	8,07	0,66
2021,0	9,67	0,65
2022,0	11,31	0,64
2023,0	13,00	0,62
2024,0	14,75	0,61
2025,0	16,56	0,59
2026,0	18,45	0,57

All results are summarized in the following table. Spectral type A2 and class V is confirmed by the position occupied on the CHR diagram (0,310 – 3,09), though the star lies slightly below the main sequence. In any case, mass of A is in reasonable accordance The mass computed with (9, III), i.e. $1,69 \mu_{\odot}$ is not too far from the value found in Appendix F for Sp=A2, i.e. $2,19 \mu_{\odot}$, but is lower than that given for the main sequence by (Pecker and Schatzman, 1959), i.e. $2,50 \mu_{\odot}$ (Sp=A2). All dynamic values are in good accordance and we can wonder from these a significant error affecting the trigonometric parallax, given as $12,2 \pm 0,65 \text{mas}$ which leads to totally unrealistic results, i.e. $\Sigma \mu_{(A+B)\text{trigo}}$ of $14,35 \mu_{\odot}$. Data from SIMBAD (van Leeuwen, 2007) $13,47 \pm 0,46 \text{mas}$ only slightly improve the picture lowering $\Sigma \mu_{(A+B)\text{trigo}}$ at $10,66 \mu_{\odot}$ in the range [9,64-11,83] μ_{\odot} .

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – HO 137							
V_{Mag}	6,02	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-1,6618	π dyn Iter/Conv.	0,02200	P prob (13,III)	544,53
(B-V) color idx	0,160	π (dyn)	0,02179	μ_A by Iter/Conv.	1,64	M^* (3,IV)	3,21
m_A	6,13	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,22791	μ_B by Iter/Conv.	0,81	V^* (4a, IV)	3,46
m_B	9,26	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,69	Σm by Iter/Conv.	2,45	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,53
Sp	A2V	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	-0,09401	d parsec	45,45	V_A (4c, IV)	3,15
Cv_A	-0,25	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	0,81	d light years	148,23	π from (5,IV)	0,02540
π trigo (mas)	13,47	$\mu_A \pi \text{dyn} + \mu_B \pi \text{dyn}$	2,50	a UA	55,19	CHR diagram	"-" ZAMS
$\Sigma \mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	10,66	$\Sigma \mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	2,52	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	2,39

Final dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $23,593\text{mas} \pm 2,556$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{\text{dyn}}}=2,487\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,038$, $\mu_{A\pi_{\text{dyn}}}=1,619 \pm 0,083$, $\mu_{B\pi_{\text{dyn}}}=0,805 \pm 0,031$.

BU 838

WDS 21209+0307, BD 02,4343, ADS 14880, HIP 105399, apparent magnitudes 7.92-10.02, Sp F8, PM +133+004. There exists an orbit by Zirm, H. (Zir2015a) with a much longer period, i.e. 1280y, than what is proposed here of 803y.

47 observations have been used by the author to compute the orbit, starting with the discovery and first observation by W. Burnham in 1881,66 and last used on 2007,627, $\theta: 153^{\circ},1$, $\rho: 1'',775$, i.e. unpublished measure by the author with a T40,6 Cassegrain reflector (Poyet, 2014), with a flat supporting the hyperbolic (F/D=26,87), a CCD and the Fourier Transform (FT) of the logarithm of the power spectrum (autocorrelation) as explained by Buil (1991), then “Reduc” (Losse, 2005) and “Surface” (Morlet and Salaman, 2005) algorithms, then $\theta^{\circ} = \text{arctg}[(x_1-x_2)/(y_1-y_2)]*(180/\pi)$ and $\rho = [(x_1-x_2)^2 + (y_1-y_2)^2]^{1/2} / 2$.

BU 838 as imaged by the author on 2007,627 $\theta: 153^{\circ},07 \pm 0,044$, $\rho: 1'',75 \pm 0,021$

BU 838 apparent ellipse drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 32,00mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – BU 838			
P=802,90	a''=2,095	A''=1,1719	C''= -1,6426
n=0,44837	i°=56,58	B''=-0,5625	H''= 0,5989
T=2414,12	Ω°=30,85	F''=1,4868	F1''= 1,3438
e=0,428	ω°=290,03	G''=1,3485	G1''= 1,2188

The following abbreviated ephemeris, with a three year interval as it is a long term period couple, is derived:

BU 838 - HIP 105399 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2016,0	155,29	1,87
2019,0	156,13	1,88
2022,0	156,95	1,89
2025,0	157,77	1,90
2028,0	158,58	1,91
2031,0	159,37	1,93
2034,0	160,16	1,94
2037,0	160,94	1,95
2040,0	161,71	1,96
2043,0	162,47	1,97

Spectral type F8 and class V are confirmed by the position occupied on the CHR diagram (0,510 – 4,56), as the star falls perfectly on the ZAMS line. Latest parallax available from SIMBAD (van Leeuwen, 2007) is $14,09 \pm 0,99$ which gives $\Sigma \mu_{(A+B)\pi\text{trigo}} = 5,10 \mu_{\odot}$, and that seems way out of the expected boundaries for such a F8V binary as taking values from Pecker and Schatzman (1959), we get $\mu_A = \mu_B = 1,19 \mu_{\odot}$, i.e. expected $\Sigma \mu = 2,38 \mu_{\odot}$, the trigonometric parallax giving a value of more than double. Expected values from Appendix F gives $\mu_A = \mu_B = 1,13 \mu_{\odot}$, i.e. expected $\Sigma \mu = 2,26 \mu_{\odot}$. All dynamical values computed are very close and coherent, be it using (9, III), (10, III), by iteration/convergence or using (7, IV).

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – BU 838							
V_{Mag}	7,86	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-1,7006	π dyn Iter/Conv.	0,02003	P prob (13,III)	940,37
(B-V) color idx	0,510	π (dyn)	0,01993	μ_A by Iter/Conv.	1,09	M^* (3,IV)	4,50
m_A	7,92	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,04619	μ_B by Iter/Conv.	0,68	V^* (4a, IV)	4,56
m_B	10,02	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,11	Σm by Iter/Conv.	1,77	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,08
Sp	F8V	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	-0,16817	d parsec	49,92	V_A (4c, IV)	4,50
Cv_A	-0,06	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	0,68	d light years	162,80	π from (5,IV)	0,02073
π trigo (mas)	14,1	$\mu_A \pi \text{dyn} + \mu_B \pi \text{dyn}$	1,79	a UA	105,13	CHR diagram	"=" ZAMS
$\Sigma \mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	5,10	$\Sigma \mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	1,80	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	0,32

Dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $20,329 \text{mas} \pm 0,571$, $\Sigma \mu_{(A+B)\pi \text{dyn}} = 1,789 \mu_{\odot} \pm 0,015$, $\mu_{A\pi \text{dyn}} = 1,094 \pm 0,018$, $\mu_{B\pi \text{dyn}} = 0,679 \pm 0,008$. Note that the probable period as determined from (13, III) of 940,37 is closer to the period of 802,9 y of this orbit than that of (Zir2015a) and that $\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$ is small for this spectral type/class and position in the CHR diagram, which comforts the dynamical results.

STF 2822 AB

WDS 21441+2845, BD 28,4169, ADS 15270, HIP 107310, apparent magnitudes 4.75-6.18, Sp initially given as F6V+G2V but last available in SIMBAD is F3V+F6V that we will use, PM +260-243. 326 observations have been used to compute the orbit, from the first starting in 1780,840 made by W. Herschel, to the last made by the author in 2007,624 with a T62cm at F/D=24,53 (Poyet et al., 2014) with a CCD and same reduction techniques as shortly mentioned above for BU 828. Only one observation by C.P. Olivier, has been corrected, as the measure was inverted by 180°, i.e. 1947,840, θ : 79°,40, ρ : 1",2. There are 3 known orbits by W.D. Heintz and J.A. Docobo, i.e. Hei1966 (P=507,5 y), Doc1987b (P=713,19 y) and Hei1995 (789 y). The orbit proposed here has a shorter period than all published orbits, i.e. of 428,0 y.

STF 2822 AB as imaged by the author with the T62cm (composite of 19 images), unpublished measure as autocorrelogram of FT(log(power spectrum)) gives 2007,624, θ : 312°,583±0,151, ρ : 1",806±0,0024

STF 2822 AB apparent ellipse drawn (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right).
Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 22,59mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C.

The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – STF 2822 AB			
P=428,00	a"=4,635	A"=0,8189	C"= 2,5470
n=0,84112	i°=75,60	B"=-3,7849	H"= -3,6970
T=1974,00	Ω °=111,93	F"=1,8625	F1"= 1,4830
e=0,605	ω °=145,44	G"=-2,0849	G1"= -1,6600

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

STF 2822 AB - HIP 107310 - [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017	328,18	1,40
2018	330,16	1,37
2019	332,24	1,34
2020	334,42	1,31
2021	336,70	1,28
2022	339,09	1,25
2023	341,58	1,22
2024	344,17	1,20
2025	346,86	1,18
2026	349,65	1,16

Spectral type F3+F6 and class V are confirmed by the position occupied on the CHR diagram (0,470 – 3,99), as the star falls nearly perfectly on the ZAMS line (just a little bit above). Latest parallax available from SIMBAD (van Leeuwen, 2007) is $44,97 \pm 0,43$ and let us believe that high accuracy has been obtained for this close star. Strangely enough, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi\text{trigo}}=5,98\mu_{\odot}$ and that seems way out of the expected boundaries for such a F3V+F6V binary as taking values from Pecker and Schatzman (1959), we get $\mu_A=1,42\mu_{\odot}$ and $\mu_B=1,28\mu_{\odot}$ i.e. expected $\Sigma\mu=2,70\mu_{\odot}$, the trigonometric parallax giving a value of more than double. Expected values from Appendix F give $\mu_A=1,32\mu_{\odot}$ and $\mu_B=1,22\mu_{\odot}$ i.e. expected $\Sigma\mu=2,54\mu_{\odot}$. All dynamical values computed are very close and coherent (9, III), (10, III), by iteration/ convergence or using (7, IV).

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – STF 2822 AB

V_{Mag}	4,50	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-1,2122	π dyn Iter/Conv.	0,06276	P prob (13,III)	506,97
(B-V) color idx	0,470	π (dyn)	0,06135	μ_A by Iter/Conv.	1,28	M^* (3,IV)	3,95
m_A	4,75	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,13579	μ_B by Iter/Conv.	0,92	V^* (4a, IV)	3,99
m_B	6,18	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,37	Σm by Iter/Conv.	2,20	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,25
Sp	F3	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	-0,03537	d parsec	15,93	V_A (4c, IV)	3,83
Cv_A	-0,05	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	0,92	d light years	51,97	π from (5,IV)	0,06554
π trigo (mas)	44,97	$\mu_A \pi_{\text{dyn}} + \mu_B \pi_{\text{dyn}}$	2,29	a UA	75,55	CHR diagram	" \approx " ZAMS
$\Sigma\mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	5,98	$\Sigma\mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	2,35	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	1,49

Dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of $63,445\text{mas} \pm 2,958$, $\Sigma\mu_{(A+B)\pi_{\text{dyn}}}=2,281\mu_{\odot} \pm 0,078$, $\mu_{A\pi_{\text{dyn}}}=1,298 \pm 0,061$, $\mu_{B\pi_{\text{dyn}}}=0,922 \pm 0,030$. Note that the probable period as determined from (13, III) is closer to the period of 428 y of this orbit than to any other periods of previous orbits before. Usually the lack of observations hinders the drawing of the ellipse, this case is the contrary as too many observations make control of each difficult and even hide somehow the final ellipse chosen.

HU 497 BC

WDS 23175+1652, BD 16,4896, ADS 16648, HIP 115002, apparent magnitudes 9.5-10.0, Sp F2III, PM +008-022. The author computed a first orbit for HU 497 BC in 2007 using the geometrical method, further to an exchange with Gili (2007) who had provided his latest measures. It happens that 3 orbits have been published since by Ling (2010) (i.e. IAUDS 161 Lin2007a, Lin2009b, Lin2010c) using the method and programs by Docobo (1985) the latest orbits being less elliptical than the first one ($e_{2007a}=0,357$, $e_{2009b}=0,313$, $e_{2010c}=0,313$).

As the last one appears still too elliptical as compared to the one the author computed in 2007 ($e=0,178$), it seems as a good test to assess the relevance of geometrical methods as compared to others approaches. The closer BC pair was distinguished by W. J. Hussey at the Lick Observatory in 1901,78 and has since described an arc of about 165° , latest observation used was by Gili, R. in 2007,822.

HU 497 BC apparent ellipse (left) and as produced by the ephemeris in the spreadsheet (right). Scale of apparent ellipse on the drawing: 1 arcsec = 185,71mm. Axes ξ and η pass through C and are in that example close to N and E.

It is now approaching its second separation maximum according to Tokovinin (1997, 1999). The orbital elements are as follow:

Orbital elements – HU 497 BC			
P=310,40	a''=0,344	A''=-0,2100	C''= -0,2481
n=1,15981	i°=131,86	B''=0,1131	H''= -0,0645
T=1974,60	Ω° =40,41	F''=0,2161	F1''= 0,2127
e=0,178	ω° =255,43	G''=0,2599	G1''= 0,2558

The following abbreviated ephemeris is derived:

HU 497 BC - HIP 115002 – [Poy2017]		
Year	θ	ρ
2017,5	260,27	0,24
2018,5	258,79	0,25
2019,5	257,35	0,25
2020,5	255,94	0,26
2021,5	254,58	0,26
2022,5	253,25	0,26
2023,5	251,95	0,27
2024,5	250,69	0,27
2025,5	249,46	0,27
2026,5	248,26	0,28

As suggested by spectral type F2III, at least A is a giant. From what was developed in section IV one knows that the MLR might not be followed well to compute satisfactorily dynamic parallax and masses. The giant status is well confirmed by the position of the star in the (B-V,V*) CHR diagram (0,494 – 3,27) and we get a striking difference between the $\Sigma\mu=0,78$ computed with (1, III) as based on trigonometric parallax and $\Sigma\mu=2,77$ as determined by the dynamic parallax (convergence algorithm) or $\Sigma\mu=3,11$ based on (1, III) and the dynamic parallax. Moreover, given the significant uncertainty affecting the trigonometric parallax, i.e. $8,14\pm 2,28\text{mas}$, the possible range for the total mass of the system, at a 68,2% confidence interval ($p\pm\text{error-in-}\pi$), is as vague as $[0,37-2,10]\mu\odot$. In any case, as this star does not obey well the MLR (i.e. it is a giant), one should be cautious reading

the dynamic results listed in the following table.

Parallaxes, Masses & Stellar evolution – HU 497 BC							
V_{Mag}	8,77	$\log \pi$ (8,III)	-2,2886	π dyn lter/Conv.	0,00535	P prob (13,III)	230,17
(B-V) color idx	0,494	π (dyn)	0,00514	μ_A by lter/Conv.	1,57	M^* (3,IV)	3,22
m_A	9,19	$\log \mu_A$ (9, III)	0,24608	μ_B by lter/Conv.	1,20	V^* (4a, IV)	3,27
m_B	10,38	$\mu_A \pi$ dyn	1,76	Σm by lter/Conv.	2,77	μ_A from (7,IV)	1,53
Sp	F2III	$\log \mu_B$ (10, III)	0,07868	d parsec	187,08	V_A (4c, IV)	2,96
Cv_A	-0,05	$\mu_B \pi$ dyn	1,20	d light years	610,17	π from (5,IV)	0,00567
π trigo (mas)	6,74	$\mu_A \pi_{dyn} + \mu_B \pi_{dyn}$	2,96	a UA	66,89	CHR diagram	"++" ZAMS
$\Sigma \mu \pi$ trigo (1,III)	1,38	$\Sigma \mu \pi$ dyn (1,III)	3,11	k (MLR)	0,0987	$\partial \log_{10} \mu_A / \partial k$	2,86

Dynamical values computed are the following: π_{dyn} of 5,408mas $\pm 0,373$, $\Sigma \mu_{(A+B)\pi_{dyn}} = 2,946 \mu_{\odot} \pm 0,169$, $\mu_{A\pi_{dyn}} = 1,620 \pm 0,125$, $\mu_{B\pi_{dyn}} = 1,199 \pm 0,063$.

VI. Conclusion

The geometrical method has been used in this paper to compute the orbits of 13 double stars, 9 of them being first-time orbits of medium to long term periods' systems. Two observations can be made: one dealing with the parallaxes, the other with the influence of the factor k of the Mass-Luminosity Relation. The next Table present a summary of the various dynamic parallaxes computed in this paper and their corresponding trigonometric parallaxes as found in SIMBAD:

Object	π_{dyn}	π_{trigo}	$\pm e - \pi_{trigo}$	$\Delta = (\pi_{dyn} - \pi_{trigo}) $	Δ in % π_{dyn}
RST 3340	9,222				
HU 616	3,354	2,57	0,61	0,784	23,38%
HU 841	6,367	7,54	1,44	1,173	18,42%
A 552	5,982	5,69	0,93	0,292	4,88%
A 2554	14,628	14,79	1,02	0,162	1,11%
BU 796	14,257	7,21	0,45	7,047	49,43%
RST 4502	4,039	3,76	0,61	0,279	6,91%
A 1097 AB	10,617	6,82	0,69	3,797	35,76%
HU 337	4,465	4,15	1,18	0,315	7,05%
HO 137	23,593	13,47	0,46	10,123	42,91%
BU 838	20,329	14,09	0,99	6,239	30,69%
STF 2822 AB	63,445	44,97	0,43	18,475	29,12%
HU 497 BC	5,408	6,74	1,45	1,332	24,63%

Mean of Δ in %: 22,86%

$\pm \sigma$ 15,66%

π_{dyn} minus π_{trigo} expressed in % of π_{dyn} and corresponding $\pm \sigma$

Their differences, i.e. π_{dyn} minus π_{trigo} , have been expressed in % of π_{dyn} . One will notice that four stars have a good match whereas the remaining show very large differences that lead to compute values of $\Sigma \mu$ with (1, III) and π_{trigo} , which are well outside a reasonable range of acceptable masses for the systems. A standard deviation of $\pm 15,66\%$ of these Δ hides the fact that we have two groups: one for which the figures are acceptable, the other delivering wild results, completely outside the expected range of reasonable values for the corresponding spectral types (all are main sequence stars, except HU 497 BC). This is a troublesome conclusion as neither the announced $\pm e - \pi_{trigo}$ nor

any other information can be used to judge *a priori* of the appropriateness of these π_{trigo} , for the computation of reliable $\Sigma\mu_s$.

Object	Sp	B-V	$\partial\log_{10}\mu_A/\partial k$
RST 3340	G3V	0,560	0,08
HU 616	F0V	0,230	3,63
HU 841	F8V	0,490	2,42
A 552	A2V	0,170	4,63
A 2554	A9V	0,345	2,04
BU 796	F2V	0,400	1,38
RST 4502	A5V	0,260	4,76
A 1097 AB	F5V	0,461	2,41
HU 337	A3V	0,310	3,68
HO 137	A0	0,160	2,39
BU 838	F8	0,510	0,32
STF 2822 AB	F5	0,470	1,49
HU 497 BC	F2III	0,494	2,86

Correlation -0,73
 Negative correlation of ((B-V), $\partial\log_{10}\mu_A/\partial k$)

The second observation deals with the factor k of the Mass-Luminosity Relation (MLR). Obtaining reliable masses by the dynamic parallax method supposes that the MLR be followed by the systems studied, which is considered to be the case for ZAMS binaries, and in that case $\partial\log_{10}\mu_A/\partial k$ should tend to zero or at least be small. Positioning the binaries studied in the CHR-diagram has confirmed that only one giant belong to this set, i.e. HU 497 BC.

Even though the residuals of the partial derivative $\partial\log_{10}\mu_A/\partial k$ were small, they did not really tend towards zero and obviously presented some correlation with the value of (B-V) as the Table above shows, the negative correlation of ((B-V), $\partial\log_{10}\mu_A/\partial k$) amounts to $-0,73$ which is very significant. The higher the value of (B-V) the lower the influence of k on the computation of the masses. The sample is small and goes from G3V to A0V, but it would be interesting to observe how the relationship evolves on a larger sample and on stars in the G4V to M4V range and to perform a sensitivity study to varying values of k .

VII. Discussion

Unless a complete revolution has been made and faultless data are available, an orbit always remains a choice trying to satisfy competing and even sometimes conflicting objectives. Fitting best the ellipse to the observations does not always lead to a satisfactory solution, i.e. one that best satisfies the law of areas as we have stressed and others also did long before us, e.g. (Danjon, 1952), (Couteau, 1978). This clearly means that in such a case, where a close system can lead to significant deviations, particularly in ρ , a solution that satisfies better the 2nd Kepler's law at the increase of the residuals (observed minus calculated, i.e. O-C) is preferable.

Minimizing the residuals is a straightforward means for the software developer to quantify in some way a solution delivered by a computer program, but as we have reminded it should only be used *after* that a consistent proposal be obtained with respect to the law of areas. Most of the time, though, the areal constant c is not as constant as one would hope and a significant dispersion is shown across the various sectors, as they are progressively tested, increasing their size and variety. Once a given c is adopted, eventually after that competing orbits be tested, using a technique such as described for RST 3340 and minimizing the standard deviation across sectors, σ_{ci} , for these

several potential orbits, a period is immediately obtained $P=S/c$ and should be checked with common sense, against the observations whenever possible.

When a value of T has been obtained, i.e. passage at periastron, from an average of several measures, one should be ready to eventually adjust it slightly (e.g. say max up to 1,5% of P) if this later improves the ephemeris and enable to reduce the residuals, especially in θ , as they are the most significant. Even though the calculations deliver perfect solutions in mathematical terms, once the orbital elements are chosen, one should remind that we start from a set of observations, often made to the limits of the instruments used by skilled observers doing their best fighting variable seeing, disturbing the measures. Of course, modern detectors and all sorts of CCDs and speckle techniques deliver more objective data, e.g. (Tokovinin *et al.*, 2014), (Tokovinin, 2016, 2017), but it will be long before we can compute orbits with intermediate periods [70-200+y] that do not rely *at all* on old but precious measures made sometimes more than a century ago, most of the time with a filar micrometer by a skilled observer, or even more often for close binaries, ρ being simply estimated at the limit of the diffraction image observed.

At the time, each astronomer who populated the files used today to compute orbits had spent more than a year learning the aspect of binaries at various magnifications when they were closer than the diffraction limit, i.e. $0,85 \cdot 14/D$ (D diameter in cm of the objective). It is amazing to notice that many exceptional observers have estimated correctly the aspect of the binaries below 50% of the resolving power of their instrument. This can be asserted from the comparison of their measures to the currently known (good grade) orbits, e.g. Schiaparelli estimating with the 50cm refractor Σ 1728 in 1898,461 at ($190^\circ/0,^{\circ}15$) when the orbit gives ($191^\circ/0,^{\circ}13$), Baize delivering consistent measures down to $0,^{\circ}18$ with a 38cm, e.g. ω Leo estimated in 1956,31 at ($224^\circ,1/0,^{\circ}19$) when the orbit gives ($223^\circ,2/0,^{\circ}18$). Still, from time to time various error factors happen, including but not limited to inversion of measures when Δm is small (i.e. contradictory quadrants), existence of unknown 3rd bodies (Genet *et al.*, 2015) and computing an orbit requires to go back to how the measures were made, to who did them, and whenever possible to go back to the notes accompanying the measures or the estimations when the values delivered are well below the resolution power.

Even though large telescopes and speckle techniques provide with higher quality measures, or even old refractors with latest cameras, e.g. EM-CCD (Gili *et al.*, 2014), (Mason, 2017), open new horizons to fainter systems with more objective and impersonal results, our bulk of data will long remain dependent on the pioneers who made double star observing an exciting discipline. In that sense, this paper suggests that computing orbits could somehow remain a craft work for intermediate to long term period's orbits, as it will be difficult for computer programs to get a feel of all what plays a role in opting for a final orbital solution. Bringing the art and science of calculating orbits together, whatever the progress made, seems probably to remain as actual than ever.

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Appendix A : on calculating sound orbits

in “Computing a double star orbital elements” (Couteau, 1978), p.119: The difficulty comes from measurements errors. Only a well trained observer, knowing the history of the observations, is able to find reasonable orbital elements from disparate measurements, too rare at some time and too numerous at others... But one needs years of experience and practice before being able to judge one or another observation of a given binary. Modern numerical processing methods are not suited to such a job. Computing an orbit will ever remain a craftsman job.

in “Calcul des éléments d’une orbite d’étoile double” (Couteau, 1978, p.119): La difficulté vient des erreurs de mesures. Seul un observateur bien entraîné, connaissant l’histoire des observations, est à même de trouver des éléments à peu près corrects à partir de mesures disparates, trop rares à certaines époques, surabondantes à d’autres... Mais il faut des années de pratique avant de savoir juger telle ou telle observation de tel couple. Les méthodes modernes de traitement numérique ne sont guère exploitables. Un calcul d’orbite d’étoile double restera toujours un travail d’artisan »

in « Differential correction of the elements » (Couteau, 1978), p.145 : The sort and importance of the deviations depend on the difficulty of the binary... This is one of the reasons why computing orbits should only be performed by regular observers, knowing well the difficulties of the measurements.

in « Correction différentielles des éléments » (Couteau, 1978), p.145 : L’allure et l’importance des écarts dépendent de la difficulté de la binaire... C’est l’une des raisons pour lesquelles les calculs d’orbites ne devraient être entrepris que par des observateurs réguliers, connaissant bien les difficultés des mesures.

in “Is This Orbit Really Necessary?” Worley (1990) laments the tendency to publish orbits of double stars that are neither reliable nor useful and imply that if more time were spent observing and less time computing, we would all be better off.

Appendix B : Correction C_v to m_v as a function of Sp type

Table Cv Harris III (1963) et Baize (1943) for M types

Sp	Cv	Sp	Cv	Sp	Cv	Sp	Cv
B5	-1,39A1		-0,32F5		-0,04K3		-0,25
B6	-1,21A2		-0,25G0		-0,06K5		-0,71
B7	-1,04A3		-0,20G5		-0,10K7		-1,02
B8	-0,85A5		-0,15G8		-0,15M0		-1,22
B9	-0,66A7		-0,12K0		-0,19M2		-1,43
A0	-0,40F0		-0,08K2		-0,25M4		-1,67

Appendix C : μ and M as a function of Spectral Type Sp

Sp	M	μ	Sp	M	μ
B7	-0,60	3,98	G1	4,50	1,70
B8	-0,30	3,68	G2	4,70	1,20
B9	0,00	3,41	G3	4,80	0,99
A0	0,30	3,16	G4	5,00	0,94
A1	0,90	2,71	G5	5,10	0,92
A2	1,30	2,50	G6	5,30	0,87
A3	1,70	2,15	G7	5,50	0,83
A4	2,00	2,04	G8	5,60	0,81
A5	2,20	1,94	G9	5,80	0,77
A6	2,40	1,84	K0	6,00	0,73
A7	2,60	1,75	K1	6,20	0,69
A8	2,80	1,66	K2	6,50	0,66
A9	2,90	1,62	K3	6,90	0,58
F0	3,10	1,58	K4	7,20	0,54
F1	3,20	1,50	K5	7,50	0,46
F2	3,30	1,46	K6	7,90	0,45
F3	3,40	1,42	K7	8,20	0,41
F4	3,50	1,39	K8	8,50	0,38
F5	3,60	1,35	K9	8,90	0,35
F6	3,80	1,28	M0	9,20	0,32
F7	3,90	1,25	M1	9,70	0,28
F8	4,10	1,19	M2	10,10	0,25
F9	4,20	1,16	M3	10,60	0,22
G0	4,40	1,10	M4	11,30	0,19

Mass μ according to Baize and Romani (1946) and absolute bolometric magnitude M as a function of Spectral Type Sp, data compiled for the main sequence from Pecker and Schatzman (1959).

Appendix D : Kepler's Law

Starting from the polar equation to an ellipse, and thus equation (7, II)

$$du/dt = \mu / (1 - e \cdot \cos u)$$

$$\mu dt = du \cdot (1 - e \cdot \cos u)$$

$$\mu dt = du - e \cdot \cos u du$$

thus by trivial integration :

$$\int \mu dt = \int du - \int e \cdot \cos u du$$

$$\mu \int dt = \int u - e \cdot \int \cos u du$$

$$\mu \int dt = u - e \cdot \sin u$$

$$\mu (t - T) = u - e \cdot \sin u$$

$M = u - e \cdot \sin u$; equation known as Kepler's Law.

Appendix E : Keplerian's Motion

Compute any value of u (eccentric anomaly) for any given e and M
(input cells in yellow)

e	0,35		
20M	0,34906585		
u0	0,4687729		u0=M+e sinM
u1	0,50719302		u1=M+e sin u0
u2	0,51906979		u2=M+e sin u1
u3	0,522691		0,735810 42,158823
u4	0,523791		0,737288 42,243504
u5	0,524124		0,737736 42,269172
u6	0,524225	30,035882	0,737872 42,276951
u7	0,524256	30,037636	0,737913 42,279307
u8	0,524265	30,038167	0,737926 42,280022
u9	0,524268	30,038328	0,737929 42,280238
u10	0,524269	30,038377	0,737931 42,280304
u11	0,524269	30,038391	0,737931 42,280323
u12	0,524269	30,038396	0,737931 42,280329
u13	0,524269	30,038397	0,737931 42,280331
u14	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u15	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u16	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u17	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u18	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u19	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u20	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u21	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u22	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u23	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u24	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u25	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u26	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u27	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u28	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u29	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
un	0,524269	30,038398	0,737931 42,280332
u rad		u deg	v rad
			v deg

$$v = 2 \arctg (\sqrt{(1+e)/(1-e)} * \tg u/2)$$

Appendix F : (B-V), V, C_b, M_b, μ, V* as a function of Sp V

Sp	Temp	(B-V)	V	C _b	M _b ¹	log μ	μ ²	V* ³
B7	14500	-0,12	-0,11	-1,04	-1,15	0,584	3,84	0,86
B8	13400	-0,09	0,22	-0,85	-0,63	0,533	3,41	1,11
B9	12400	-0,06	0,55	-0,66	-0,11	0,482	3,03	1,35
A0	10800	0,00	1,10	-0,40	0,70	0,402	2,52	1,77
A1	10200	0,03	1,26	-0,32	0,94	0,378	2,39	1,89
A2	9730	0,06	1,57	-0,25	1,32	0,341	2,19	2,14
A3	9260	0,09	1,75	-0,20	1,55	0,318	2,08	2,28
A4	8940	0,12	1,93	-0,18	1,75	0,298	1,99	2,42
A5	8620	0,15	2,10	-0,15	1,95	0,278	1,90	2,56
A6	8405	0,18	2,22	-0,14	2,09	0,265	1,84	2,66
A7	8190	0,20	2,34	-0,12	2,22	0,252	1,79	2,76
A8	7795	0,24	2,57	-0,11	2,46	0,223	1,67	2,94
A9	7481	0,28	2,82	-0,09	2,73	0,197	1,57	3,15
F0	7240	0,33	3,10	-0,08	3,02	0,173	1,49	3,39
F1	7085	0,36	3,26	-0,07	3,19	0,157	1,43	3,52
F2	6930	0,38	3,41	-0,06	3,35	0,140	1,38	3,64
F3	6732	0,40	3,51	-0,05	3,46	0,122	1,32	3,71
F4	6603	0,42	3,65	-0,05	3,60	0,108	1,28	3,83
F5	6540	0,45	3,82	-0,04	3,78	0,098	1,25	3,98
F6	6540	0,47	3,94	-0,04	3,90	0,086	1,22	4,08
F7	6320	0,50	4,11	-0,04	4,07	0,069	1,17	4,23
F8	6200	0,53	4,28	-0,05	4,23	0,053	1,13	4,37
F9	6060	0,57	4,47	-0,06	4,42	0,035	1,08	4,53
G0	5920	0,60	4,66	-0,06	4,60	0,017	1,04	4,69
G1	5850	0,62	4,77	-0,07	4,70	0,007	1,02	4,78
G2	5780	0,64	4,87	-0,07	4,80	-0,003	0,99	4,87
G3	5666	0,65	4,89	-0,08	4,81	-0,014	0,97	4,87
G4	5610	0,66	4,97	-0,09	4,88	-0,020	0,96	4,93
G5	5610	0,68	5,09	-0,10	4,99	-0,022	0,95	5,05
G6	5514	0,69	5,12	-0,12	5,00	-0,032	0,93	5,06
G7	5475	0,70	5,20	-0,13	5,07	-0,038	0,92	5,13
G8	5490	0,72	5,33	-0,15	5,18	-0,040	0,91	5,26
G9	5365	0,77	5,64	-0,17	5,47	-0,068	0,86	5,52
K0	5240	0,81	5,94	-0,19	5,75	-0,097	0,80	5,78
K1	5010	0,87	6,17	-0,22	5,95	-0,116	0,77	5,98
K2	4780	0,92	6,40	-0,25	6,15	-0,136	0,73	6,17
K3	4590	0,98	6,70	-0,35	6,35	-0,156	0,70	6,44
K4	4280	1,08	7,13	-0,53	6,60	-0,180	0,66	6,83
K5	3970	1,18	7,56	-0,71	6,85	-0,205	0,62	7,22
K6	3769	1,24	7,94	-0,75	7,20	-0,228	0,59	7,58
K7	3631	1,29	8,23	-0,77	7,46	-0,244	0,57	7,86
K8	3503	1,33	8,52	-0,80	7,72	-0,259	0,55	8,14
K9	3346	1,39	8,91	-0,84	8,07	-0,279	0,53	8,50
M0	3236	1,44	9,20	-0,86	8,33	-0,294	0,51	8,78
M1	3070	1,51	9,67	-0,91	8,76	-0,317	0,48	9,23
M2	2948	1,57	10,05	-0,94	9,11	-0,334	0,46	9,60
M3	2809	1,64	10,53	-0,99	9,54	-0,355	0,44	10,05
M4	2635	1,75	11,18	-1,05	10,13	-0,383	0,41	10,68

¹ Absolute bolometric magnitude $M_b = V + C_b$

² Unit in Solar Mass μ_{\odot}

³ Reduced absolute magnitude $V^* = V + (5/3) \cdot \log_{10} \mu$

History of Corrections:

- July 13, 2025: Orbital elements of HO 137 p. 28 were wrong, they had been duplicated from those of HU 137. Thanks to Andreas Alzner for having detected that misprint.
- July 14, 2025: Equation (14, III) p. 11 was incorrect.
- July 16, 2025: $\alpha^3 = p^3 P^2$ is wrong and corrected in p 9, before equation (6, III) as $\alpha^3 = a^3 / P^2$
- July 17, 2025: All equations with numbers as fractions were ambiguous after (6, III) and corrected to remove ambiguities in p. 9 and p. 10
- July 17, 2025: “and then a new value of the parallax p from (14, III)” corrected to read instead (13, III) p. 10
- July 19, 2025: Instead of $3 \log_{10} = \log_{10} ((1 - R) \alpha^3) - \log_{10} \mu_A$ read: $3 \log_{10} p = \log_{10} ((1 - R) \alpha^3) - \log_{10} \mu_A$ p. 11
- July 21, 2025: The reference Arend (1970) p. 1 is missing in the list of references. It looks like I was making a reference to this paper instead (1968). Citation and reference adjusted.
<https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1968CORBA...5.....A/abstract>
- July 21, 2025: The reference Argyle, R. W., 2012 was not cited in the text, so it was removed from the list of references.
- July 22, 2025: “*Mass of A as computed from (7, VI)*” p. 16 – should read instead (7, IV)
- July 23, 2025: A citation for “(Gili and Bonneau, 2001)” that was into the list of references was added into the text.
- July 23, 2025: Law of areas instead “law of the areas”.
- July 23, 2025: Malkov, 1977 was wrongly referenced instead of Malkov et al. 1997 and not cited in the text, thus removed from the list of references. Same for de Grijs, R., 2011 and Novakovic, B., 2007. ISBN of Perryman, M., et al., 2009 corrected, citation (Russell, 1938) was corrected to (Russell, 1928), (Russell and Moore, 1940) p. 8 was corrected to (Russell and Moore, 1940) The citation “Mason, B. D., and Hartkopf, W. I., 2017” that had been omitted was added into the text. URL has been corrected for Mason B. D., Wycoff, G., and Hartkopf, W. I. 2003, <https://crf.usno.navy.mil/wdstext>
- July 24, 2025: The reference Tatum, J. B., 2017 has been updated as the website address has changed. And has become : Tatum, J. B., 2023 (latest update of website). Turner, N. H., Barry, D. J., & McAlister, H. A., 1992 and van den Bos, W. H., 1926. Orbital elements of binary systems were not cited in the text and thus removed from the list of references.
- July 25, 2025: Important equations that have been numbered have been replaced using an equation editor to make them more readable. This may involve some repagination.
- July 25, 2025: Equation $\log_{10} P = (3/2) \cdot \log_{10} a - (1/2) \cdot \log_{10} D - (k/2) M_{\odot} + M_A((k/2)-3/10) + 3/10 (m_{VA} + C_{VA}) + 3/2$ (13, III) p. 10 was wrongly labeled (13, III) instead of (12, III) and wrongly used in the next sentence as (13, III) instead of (12, III).
- July 25, 2025: The sentence “*Replacing in (2, III) M^*A by its value as defined in (2, IV)*” is replaced by “Extracting M_A from (2, IV), i.e. $M_A = M^*_A - (5/3) \log_{10} \mu_A$ and replacing in (2, III) M_A by its value as defined in (2, IV)” p. 13.
- July 25, 2025: Various typos in last § of IV “Stellar evolution assessed with binaries’ orbits” p. 14 where “has” is replaced by “as”. Typo p. 27 replace “systematically to short” with “systematically too short”.
- July 31, 2025: The ephemeris of STF2822AB was off by 180° in θ (classical ambiguity in the excel spreadsheet) and was corrected thanks to Andreas Alzner who spotted the mistake.

IN MEMORIAM

René GILI

(1951–2018)

A Life Dedicated to Double Stars

The history of observational astronomy is punctuated not only by great discoveries but also by the quiet, persistent work of those who devote their lives to the patient accumulation of precise measurements. Among them, René Gili occupies a special place. For decades, he stood as one of the most skilled and passionate observers of double and multiple stars in Europe, carrying forward a tradition that began with the great refractors of the 19th century.

Born on August 17, 1951, René grew up in an era when professional and amateur astronomy were still deeply interconnected. His early passion for the night sky matured into a lifelong vocation: the study of visual binaries, one of the oldest yet most fundamental branches of stellar astronomy. René's association with the 74 cm Great Refractor of the Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur in Nice marked the culmination of this legacy. Long after many had declared such instruments obsolete, he demonstrated that, in capable hands, they could still produce world-class results. At a time when adaptive optics and space telescopes dominated the headlines, René showed that careful application of modern techniques—CCD imaging and speckle interferometry—could breathe new life into historical telescopes.

His most celebrated contribution was the design and construction of PISCO2, the new speckle camera that replaced the original PISCO instrument. This was not a mere institutional project—it was, to a large extent, a personal one. René invested his own resources to bring PISCO2 to life, collaborating with professional engineers and astronomers such as Jean-Louis Prieur, Daniel Bonneau, and Jean-Pierre Rivet. The instrument featured an EMCCD detector, enabling high-speed, low-noise observations that dramatically improved the resolution and accuracy of binary-star measurements at the Nice 76 cm refractor. Through his perseverance, René ensured that the Nice refractor remained scientifically relevant well into the 21st century. His work, documented in numerous papers published in *Observations & Travaux*, the *Journal of Double Star Observations*, and *The Observatory*, contributed hundreds of precise measurements to the Washington Double Star Catalog (WDS). He also helped sustain a fragile bridge between professional astronomers and highly skilled amateurs—a community where passion often outweighs resources.

Then, in 2018, came the end of this chapter. The Observatory's priorities shifted toward heritage preservation and public outreach. Scientific use of the 74 cm refractor was discontinued, despite seeing conditions and sky brightness remaining essentially unchanged from previous decades. For René, this decision carried a profound weight. He had invested not only years of his life but also his personal finances and hopes into an observing program that suddenly ceased to exist. In August 2018, René Gili passed away under these sad circumstances. His body was discovered two months later on Oct 12, a fact that speaks silently of the solitude he endured in his final days. While the exact details may never be known, many of us who knew him cannot separate his death from the heartbreak of seeing his life's work brutally interrupted when those were supposed to be his golden years of observations as he could be full time as he had retired.

I had known René since 1977. He was working in a workshop at the time and supplied me with the materials (profiled irons, resin sheets, etc.) to build the shelter for my first 307mm Cassegrain F/D=30 telescope, it was in 1981. To me, he was more than a colleague; he was a friend, a man of immense curiosity, remarkable technical skill and unwavering dedication. His name rarely appeared in glossy journals or at large conferences, yet his contribution was invaluable. Every precise position angle and separation, every differential magnitude he measured was an act of fidelity to a scientific tradition that is as old as modern astronomy itself.

René leaves behind not only a body of published work but also unpublished data that must be preserved and should also be processed and published. These observations, representing years of effort, should not vanish into silence. They are part of his legacy and, in a sense, his voice.

When I finished this work on double stars in the summer of 2017⁵, I sent it to him and he didn't reply. I was surprised but figured he was busy and life went on, returning to Malta and embarking on writing a climate book that took all my energy. I didn't realize that I could have been a help, especially as the instruments at my private observatory in Caussols were little used and we could have adapted them, maybe not for PISCO2, but for another camera and the adventure would have continued. At a time when the difference in means between professionals and amateurs has never been greater, since the use of all kinds of interferometric techniques, it's important to remember the satisfaction that an orbit calculation can bring to anyone who gives themselves the means to achieve it. This article is both a testimony and an incentive and this paper is dedicated to René.

It is both a tribute and a farewell—not only to a friend but to a chapter of my own life intertwined with his. As long as there are observers who, on clear nights, turn their telescopes toward double stars, the name of René Gili will not be forgotten.

Requiescat in pace.

Nice, July 24, 2025.

⁵ Original DOI on Aug. 24, 2017 was 10.13140/RG.2.2.35677.92647/1 but it was lost while making an update of the paper, thus I am now using a Zenodo DOI instead enabling versioning.